

List of policy recommendations: current national and EU policies related to EOMs

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AUTHORS:	Maria Valentina Lasorella, Irene Criscuoli, Ilaria Falconi, Francesca Varia, Daniela Quarato, Assunta Amato, Giovanni Dara Guccione
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ABSTRACT

This deliverable aims to identify similarities and differences in current national and EU policies related to EOMs strategies and policy instruments adopted in the seven countries participating in the EOM4SOIL project. Policy instruments which are consistent with the production and use of EOMs as amendments, and which have potential positive impacts on the sustainable agricultural soil management have been analysed in more detail. The document therefore provides an analytical framework and recommendations which can be useful to support the decisions of policy makers, farmers and other key stakeholders at both national and local levels.

Executive summary

This work aims at analysing the current European and national regulatory framework about exogenous organic matter (EOM) production and use in soils and identifying barriers (regulatory obstacles, lack of knowledge, conflicting interests, etc.) which hamper the EOMs value chain development (both from the production and use perspectives). The “e” of EOM defines “external” and is OM added to soil as fertilizer that did not origin from the same field as applied and/or has undergone transformations.

In line with the EOM4SOIL project, it also aims at proposing policy solutions and actions to overcome the identified barriers and spread best management practices of organic matter for soil amendment to contribute to climate change mitigation and improve soil health. Therefore, data collected during the project referred to manure, slurry, compost, sewage sludge, digestate and biochar and were gathered from different countries (Austria, Belgium, Italy, Finland, France, Lithuania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and Turkey). The methodology consists in a survey conducted by submitting questionnaires to representatives of each country involved in EOM4SOIL. Respondents are asked to prioritize policies from the candidate list in addressing/influencing the production and use of four candidate EOM’ amendments (biochar, digestate, compost and manure). A comparison among the countries presented highlights strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats for each EOMs supply chain and identify main needs and barriers to the production, use and application of EOMs as soil improver. In addition, a list of policy recommendations, coming from the analysis at national and EU level have been defined to regulate or provide guidance for use of fertilisers in farming.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

EU	European Union
GHGs	Green House Gasses
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
EOM	External Organic Matter
AECM	Agri-environment-climate Measure
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
AT	Agricultural transition
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
EC	European Commission
EIP-Agri	European Innovation Partnership - Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EOM	External Organic Matter
EU	European Union
FSN	Food Security and Nutrition
GAEC	Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition
GPP	Green Public Procurement
IPARD	Instrument for pre-accession Assistance
MS	Member State
OG	Operational Group
PDO	Protected Designation of origin
PGI	Protected Geographical Indication
PPP	Polluter Pays Principle
SMR	Statutory Management Requirement
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
WFD	Water Framework Directive

Introduction

This report investigates the way how existing European, national and regional policies support and incentivize a sustainable adoption of EOMs as amendment in agricultural soils. It brings out gaps or needs for revision/update of existing policies related to EOM production and uses to overcome the existing barriers which hamper the development of a sustainable value chain of EOMs at EU and MS. It has particularly been done starting from the rules set by the EU Regulation on the marketing of fertilizers (Reg. EU No. 2019/1009¹) and the implementing regulations and guidelines that have been accompanied it since its entry into force (July 2022). At a strategic level, the most crucial EU framework of reference is the EU Green Deal, which outlines binding climate targets that all economic sectors, from industry to agriculture, must contribute to achieving climate neutrality by 2050. That means working to ensure first reducing the need to use chemical fertilizers, which is the one of the objectives of our study.

The first section outlines the scope of the study. It identifies the main policy trajectories that intersect with the topic of EOMs, as well as the key issues addressed by farmers, suppliers, and other stakeholders in producing or using EOMs as amendments. The methodology used for this piece of research was based on a desk analysis guided by a conceptual framework to select the amendments to be analysed. The second section shows the results obtained from processing data collected through questionnaires, focusing on the differences and similarities in the implementation of the Reg. (EU) n. 2019/1009 at the MS level. This section also examines policy gaps, solutions and recommendations to address existing barriers that, according to representatives from EOM4SOIL partner countries, hamper the production and use of EOM amendments across different geographical contexts.

The last section concludes with some general considerations about the factors that contribute to influencing the production and the use of EOM fertilizers across the EU, and with a list of the main policy recommendations (Sub-task 6.2.2) highlighted during the 2-years of investigation.

The authors of this report hope that this list will be useful to support the work of the EU Commission in drafting its report on implementation and impact of the Reg. 2019/1009 due in July 2026 (in accordance with Article 49 of that Regulation).

¹ [Regulation \(EU\) 2019/1009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products and amending Regulations \(EC\) No 1069/2009 and \(EC\) No 1107/2009 and repealing Regulation \(EC\) No 2003/2003](#)

1. Scope and boundaries of the study

1.1 Conceptual framework for EOM policy analysis

The European research project “External organic matters for climate mitigation and soil health” (EOM4SOIL), funded by the European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management (EJP SOIL), aims at proposing best management practices for the pre-processing and application of external organic matters (EOMs) to agricultural soils as amendments. This approach aspires to contribute to climate change mitigation and improve soil health.

In this context, "external" refers to organic matter added to the soil as a fertiliser which originates outside the field where it is applied and/or has undergone specific transformations.

The present study aims to:

- assess the current European and national regulatory frameworks governing the production and application of EOM in soils, and

- identify regulatory barriers which hinder the development of the EOM value chain, from both production and use perspectives.

Research has focused particularly on key EOMs traditionally used in agriculture (such as manure and slurry) as well as innovative, with significant potential for improving soil health and, subsequently, agricultural productivity and sustainability (i.e., compost, sewage sludge, digestate and biochar). These EOMs have been investigated according to three main criteria: a) raw materials (e.g. biowastes, manures, or industrial wastes); b) production processes of EOMs (e.g., anaerobic digestion, composting, or carbonization); c) potential agronomic benefits and limitations.

Regarding this last point, it can be affirmed that the current level of knowledge on the agronomic effects of EOM application remains low, not only among farmers but also within the research community, which has limited access to long-term experimental results across a broader range of crops.

The effects of applying EOMs to agricultural soils depend on the characteristics of EOMs themselves, pedoclimatic conditions, frequency of application and cropping systems. Key benefits include carbon (C) return to soils and potential C storage after repeated applications, enhanced soil fertility, improved biological activity, physical and chemical soil properties (Obriot et al., 2016). EOMs can also reduce environmental impacts by substituting for mineral fertilizers (Buckwell and Nadeu, 2016), and decreasing waste production, thereby contributing

positively to the environment. Additionally, the development of new businesses can create positive economic spin-off at the territorial level.

However, there are potential downsides, such as soil contamination by heavy metals, pathogens, and microplastics (Schmidt et al., 2016). Inadequate EOM management practices may lead to additional environmental negative impacts, including nitrate leaching, air pollution, and emissions of greenhouse gas (GHGs) (Guenet et al., 2021).

Table 1 presents an example of the conceptual framework employed to examine selected soil improvers—namely, digestate, compost, biochar, and some of their combinations—classified here as “high potential”.

		Production process of the selected EOM		
		<i>Anaerobic digestion</i>	<i>composting</i>	<i>carbonization</i>
Possible effect of EOM application	<i>Increase soil Carbon</i>			
	<i>Water retention stability</i>	Digestate	Biochar	Biochar
	<i>Increase soil structure</i>	Digestate + compost	Compost	Biochar
	<i>Increase biodiversity and soil organic matter</i>	Digestate + compost	Biochar	Biochar + compost

The main reason which has led us to select biochar, compost and digestate lies on the fact that, if they meet certain standards, they provide organic matter and nutrients that improve suboptimal or even poor condition of arable soils and consequently their overall fertility. These aspects make them viable solutions and increasingly demanded products by farmers. While digestate is mostly used in the agricultural sector due to its characteristics, compost and biochar are also employed in other markets – although with a lower share – for instance as growing media as substitute of peat, whose extraction greatly contributes to climate change (Gilbert & Siebert, 2022). On the other hand, biochar is proving extremely effective at improving the water retention capacity and quality of soils (e.g, structure and biodiversity). The high surface area of biochar also contributes to reduce nitrogen leaching and dissolved organic carbon.

1.2. Data collection and methodology

During the EOM4SOIL project, data were gathered from several participating countries, including Austria, Belgium, Italy, Finland, France, Lithuania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and Turkey. The methodology involved a survey conducted through questionnaires distributed to MS experts from diverse geographic locations in the EU, reaching a total of 5 MS. The 5 MS represent from north, centre and south EU.

To collect comprehensive data on both European and national policy frameworks, this section briefly describes the approach used to investigate policy gaps, barriers, current solutions, and policy recommendations aimed at overcoming challenges related to the production and use of EOMs as soil amendments. A specific questionnaire, designed in collaboration with EOM4SOIL partners, was developed to address relevant soil-related policies in the EU and reference countries, incorporating both open and closed questions. This combination enabled the collection of quantitative and qualitative data, resulting in a more complete and in-depth analysis.

The questionnaire was divided into three sections. The first section provided a preliminary list of policies believed to impact the production and use of selected EOM amendments (Table 2). Respondents were asked to expand this list and prioritise policies and policy instruments that influence or directly address the production and use of four key EOMs: manure, digestate, compost, and biochar.

Table 2 – Preselection of policies affecting the production and the use of EOM’ amendments in Europe.

TYOLOGY	DENOMINATION	DESCRIPTION
Sectorial compliance - rules influencing the production of EOM’ amendments	New regulation on fertilizers (EU Reg. 2019/1009)	Rules the production and commercialization of EOM amendments and other fertilizers throughout Europe
	Waste framework Directive (EU Directive 2018/851)	Defines when waste ceases to be waste and it becomes a secondary raw material, byproducts

Sectorial compliance - rules influencing the use of EOM' amendments	Sewage sludge Directive (EU Directive 86/278/CEE)	Defines the conditions under which sewage sludge can be used for agronomic benefits in agriculture
	Hygiene of foodstuff (CE Reg. n. 1907/2006)	Defines minimum rules to minimize the risk of contamination of food products
	Contamination of foodstuff	Defines the maximum level of certain contaminants in food products
Territorial compliance - rules defining restrictions for uses in sensitive areas	Nitrate Directive (n. 91/676/CEE), Habitat Directive, Water framework directive NEC Directive (n. 2016/2284), EU Soil Strategy 2030.	Defines management restrictions, including fertilizers uses for sensitive areas
Supportive instruments - rules for financing actions facilitating compliance	Common Agricultural Policy	Incentivize sustainable practices, including subsidies for the management of soil fertility
	Cohesion and Rural Development policies	Incentivize individual and/or community facilities to recover organic waste
	Renewable Energy Directive II (n. 2018/2001)	Directive promotes the production of energy also from biogas, encouraging, among other things, the production of significant quantities of digestate which end up on agricultural land (production and use of organic fertilisers) Directive on the promotion of the use of renewable sources. It guarantees financial support for renewable energies and sets sustainability and greenhouse gas emission reduction criteria for biofuels, bioliquids and biomass fuels.

In addition to the survey, an extensive desk analysis of sector-specific regulations was conducted. This analysis began by examining the implementation status of EU Regulation 2019/1009. Information was gathered from the NANDO database (European Commission, 2023) regarding the presence of national notifying authorities responsible for ensuring regulatory compliance in each Member State (MS). The absence of these authorities indicates non-transposition of the regulation.

In the second step, we compared the threshold values for contaminants set at the EU level under Reg. EU n. 2019/1009 with national threshold provided in the D5.1 database. This comparison has helped to assess the stringency of to existing national rules on contaminants in EOMs with respect to the European regulation. In addition, qualitative pieces of information on policy gaps, solutions and recommendations were classified according to three main scopes: policy instruments affecting EOM production, policy instruments affecting EOM use as soil amendments, other policy instruments which can have an indirect impact on the production or use of EOMs.

Finally, the main drivers identified by key stakeholders interviewed (suppliers, farmers, researchers, etc.) as positively or negatively influencing the development of EOM value chains were analysed. The resulting policy recommendations are based on an assessment of these drivers, with particular attention to the quality and quantity of raw materials available at the territorial level, which are crucial for the development of value chains.

Figure 2: Cross-cutting legislation scheme

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Source: data from BIOBEST, 2024

On 16 July 2019, the European Commission has published Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 (Fertilising Products Regulation – FPR), which replaced and repealed the previous Regulation (EC) No. 2003/2003 establishing the conditions for making fertilisers available on the internal market (REGULATION (EU) 2019/1009 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL, 2019). The EU Fertilising Products Regulation (EU, 2019) is intended to create a policy framework to encourage the use of organic fertilisers and soil improvers, thereby decreasing the EU's dependency on imports of mineral fertilisers and contributing to a circular economy for nutrients. According to the latest version of the FPR, a fertilising product is defined as “a substance, mixture, micro-organism or any material, applied or intended to be applied on plants or their rhizosphere or on mushrooms or their mycosphere, or intended to constitute the rhizosphere or mycosphere, either on its own or mixed with other material for the purpose of providing the plants or mushrooms with nutrients or improving their nutrient efficiency.”. Regulation’s main objectives consist in fostering the use of organic and waste-derived fertilising products and bringing them at a level playing field with mineral fertilisers, creating new market opportunities and tackling environmental concerns not addressed by previous legislation.

By fulfilling the requirements of the regulation, compost and digestate-based fertilising products (organic fertiliser, soil improver and growing media) can be placed on the European market. The European Union's robust policy framework for water conservation in Europe was a focal point considering the impact of the use of their EOMs on different ecosystem services, such as, soil, water, air, biodiversity, etc. Key instruments, including the Water Framework Directive, Nitrates Directive, and Water Reuse Regulation, have been discussed. Additionally, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) was highlighted as a mechanism through which the EU promotes policy implementation and incentivizes farmers to adopt sustainable-friendly practices.

The European Union (EU) has recognized the importance of sustainable fertilization management and has put in place a robust policy framework to address this issue. The policy framework connected with EU Fertilising Products Regulation is based on three key instruments of European water conservation policy: the Water Framework Directive (including connected directives, i.e. Groundwater Directive), the Nitrates Directive, and the Water Reuse Regulation. Additionally, the EU promotes the implementation of these directives through the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) via cross-compliance measures and voluntary measures and to the description of example fiches in Rural Development Programmes. The Nitrates Directive, was introduced in 1991 and revised in 2018, specifically addresses water pollution from agricultural sources. It aims to protect water quality by regulating the use of nitrates from agricultural activities, including livestock farming and fertilization. Member states are required to designate vulnerable zones, implement action programs to reduce nitrate pollution, and establish measures such as nutrient management plans and restrictions on fertilizer use. Finally, the latest regulation considered is the Water Reuse Regulation (741/2020); it is a recent addition to EU water policy, adopted to encourage the safe and sustainable reuse of treated wastewater for agricultural irrigation. It sets out

quality standards for reused water and establishes a framework for risk assessments and monitoring to ensure public health and environmental protection. This regulation promotes water reuse, reducing the pressure on freshwater resources. Therefore, even if not directly connected to the implementation of water conservation practices at the farm level, it can contribute to the sustainable use of water resources in the pilot areas selected by working groups.

Finally, attention was given also to the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) which, between else, is a significant mechanism through which the EU promotes the implementation of the Soil management, Water Framework Directive, Nitrates Directive, etc. The CAP incorporates cross-compliance measures that require farmers to adhere to environmental and sustainability standards, including those related to soil management practices and increase soil organic content at farm level. Farmers receiving CAP subsidies must comply with relevant regulations, such as BCCA, or GAEC or Nitrates Directive, to mitigate the impact of crop management on natural resources. Non-compliance can result in reduced or withheld subsidies, incentivizing farmers to adopt sustainable-friendly practices. The CAP also offers financial support for voluntary agri-environmental measures which are strictly related to soil management and increase carbon content in the soil. Farmers can access funding for initiatives that go beyond regulatory requirements and contribute to soil conservation. These measures can include implementing innovative techniques for soil management, adopting sustainable farming practices that reduce organic carbon consumption.

In our specific case, the Nitrate Directive, adopted in 2020, is a cornerstone of European policy. It established the holistic approach to fertilization management, focusing on agricultural aspect as the key planning and management. National rules for fertilisers and soil improvers may continue to exist and, where there is bilateral recognition of these rules, Member States may still export materials that comply with national product requirements.

Its rules will affect companies in EU Member States that want to export compost or soil improvers, fertilisers and growing media based on compost or dried digestate to other EU Member States. From 16 July 2020 onwards, exporting producers need certification (CE marking) of their products. Some criteria for this certification are very clear. For example, bio-waste that is not collected separately, sewage sludge and industrial sludge are not allowed as input materials.

In table 1 we provide an indicative, although not exhaustive, classification of policy instruments which could contribute to addressing the management of agricultural soil in the EU and Türkiye according to the principle related to the final objective of soil amendments, increase the soil organic content. These policy areas are: Incentivising the adoption of sustainable practices; Enabling participatory processes for sustainable development; Regulating the protection of the environment and the landscape; Co-creation and sharing of innovation and knowledge; Triggering new market opportunities.

Table 1 - A classification of the policy instruments increasing the SOM in soil

Policy Areas	Description of the main policy instruments
Incentivising the adoption of sustainable practices (<i>improvement of agricultural soils</i>)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAP investments to purchase equipment for sustainable production methods
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAP schemes for the climate, the environment and animal welfare (so called “eco-schemes”) • AEC measures within the CAP and IPARD
Enabling participatory processes for sustainable development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Priority access to public support for collective actions • Other measures within the CAP and IPARD (Turkey)
Regulating the protection of the environment and the landscape	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules to monitor and manage environmental pressures to safeguard soil (<i>vulnerable zones such as Nitrate vulnerable zones</i>)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules aimed at protecting agricultural land from land take, soil sealing and landscape degradation
Co-creation and sharing of knowledge and innovation (AKIS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot projects by the Operational Groups of PEI – Agri • Living Labs and Lighthouses under the Horizon Europe programme
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farm advisory services and technical assistance • Training, including coaching and exchange of best practices
Triggering new market opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actions to promote green public procurement • Actions to promote local farmer markets
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon credit schemes

Source: CREA, adaptation from Deliverable 4.1 into dialogue, 2024

At European level there are several instruments belonging under the policy area ‘Incentives for the adoption of sustainable practices’ protecting soil and increasing the SOM at farm level. These instruments are designed in compliance with the EU regulations but are co-financed and implemented by MSs according to their national (or regional) priorities, whether they are under the Strategic Plan of the CAP 2023-2027 or, in the case of the Turkish Government, under the IPARD III Program (best management practices, such as GAEC, Best Management Practices (BMP), etc. Generally, participatory processes are addressed by means of two main complementary instruments: grants and aids, and the legal empowerment of groups of actors or networks with certain common goals. Grants and aids are provided by means of financial instruments (e.g., under the national Strategic Plan of the CAP 2023-2027, the Turkish IPARD program or the LIFE Program), which often provide priority access to collective actions addressing environmental soil-related issues (e.g., grants for the construction of reservoirs or other infrastructure to incorporate organic matter to the soil, fertilization directive for the use of different amendment, such as manure).

Some of them contribute to setting the new conditionality system, which “links full receipt of CAP support to the compliance of farmers and other beneficiaries with basic standards

concerning the environment, climate change, public health, plant health and animal welfare”². In other words, the CAP only provides payments covering commitments which go beyond the relevant SMRs and GAECs (statutory management requirements (SMRs), such as good agricultural and environmental conditions (GAECs). SMRs imply compliance with the Union law, including relevant Directives in force (nitrates, water, sludge, animal welfare etc.), while the GAEC standards imply compliance with the minimum management rules for farmers and other beneficiaries set by MSs to ensure that all agricultural areas, including land which is no longer used for production purposes, are maintained in good agricultural and environmental condition³.

The policy area ‘Co-creation and sharing of knowledge and innovation’ allow facing knowledge barriers. The instruments under this policy area can be divided into three categories: aids for innovative pilot projects implemented by the GOs of the European network of PEI-Agri; aids for the provision of farm advisory services and technical assistance, as well as training, coaching and exchange of best practices in Italy we found more than 150 OG on fertilization and use of organic amendments and distribution.

The potential of these instruments in accompanying the adoption of sustainable management practices is broadly recognised, as they contribute to improving intangible assets such as skills, knowledge, attitudes and relationships. Particularly, the collaborative process of co-creation of knowledge is increasingly gaining recognition within the science, practice, and movement of agroecology: it fosters participatory learning and development, which differs from passive knowledge sharing. In addition, “when engaged in knowledge co-creation, farmers are identified in a variety of contexts as innovators who inspire and lead bottom-up transitions within their communities” .

The policy area ‘Triggering new market opportunities’ allows it to face trade barriers. Farmers are often locked into contractual relationships that prevent them from adopting sustainable practices. These instruments usually take the form of EU, national and regional laws to protect and valorise traditional productions (e.g. production specifications for PDO or PGI products), facilitate the creation of local value chains and to strengthen local brands in the global market. Other key contractual instruments are voluntary certification schemes, which include feedstock and supply chains for bioenergy, but also for food, feed and biomaterials (Meyer, 2017; Ting et al., 2016), and more recently carbon farming (Criscuoli et al., 2023).

² This quote comes from the recital 41 of the Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the CAP Strategic Plans.

³ SMRs and GAECs standard are listed in the Annex III of the Regulation (EU) 2021/2115.

Table 3 – Questionnaire, preselection of policies affecting the production and the use of EOM’ amendments in Europe.

Survey on the policy framework on the production and use of EOMs in EU

The present survey refers to compost, sewage sludge, digestate and biochar and has the aim to:

- evaluate the current European and national regulatory framework about organic matter production and use in soils and to
- identify the regulatory obstacles that hamper the value chain development (both from the production and use perspectives)

The survey is divided into three sections and is made up of open and closed-answer questions:

- Section 1 – General information.
- Section 2_Policy Analysis_EU and MS;
- Section 3 – Barriers to the development of the production and use value-chain of EOMs

The analysis has been made first at European level, comparison between MS on both from the production and use perspectives of different EOMs have been defined.

2.2.3.1 Description of the EU policy framework influencing the production and use of EOM’ amendments

EOM: Digestate

2.1.1 What’s the European regulatory framework about the production of the EOM you are referring to, so that it can be used as a soil amendment?

Name of the policy	New European Regulation on Fertilizers EU Regulation 2019:1009 NOTE: National regulations are not cancelled
Date of entry into force of the policy at EU level	Entry into force: June 5, 2019 Application: July 16, 2022 This act has been changed. Current consolidated version: 16/03/2023 It amends the Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 It repeals the Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003.
Date of transposition at national level	Not yet transposed
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive)	Regulatory

Short description of the policy
(general objective, scope of
action, ecc...)

This Regulation lays down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilizing products.

It applies to EU fertilising products, excluding animal by-products, referring to substances, mixture, micro-organism or any other material with the purpose of providing the plants or mushrooms with nutrients, which are CE marked when made available on the market.

More specifically the regulation applies to the Product Function Categories (PFCs) (Annex 1):

PFC 1: Fertilizer (organic, organo-mineral, inorganic)

PFC 2: Calcium and/or magnesium correctives

PFC 3: Soil improvers (organic and inorganic)

PFC 4: Growing substrate

PFC 5: Inhibitors (nitrification and urease)

PFC 6: Plant bio stimulants (microbial and non-microbial)

PFC 7: Physical mixture of fertilizing products (previous points 1-6)

An EU fertilising product shall consist solely of the component materials (CMCs) listed in Annex II:

CMC 1: Substances and mixtures based on raw material

CMC 2: Plants, plant parts or plant extracts

CMC 3: Compost

CMC 4: Fresh crop digestate

CMC 5: Digestate different from that of fresh crops

CMC 6: By-products of the food industry

CMC 7: Microorganisms

CMC 8: Nutrient polymers

CMC 9: Polymers other than nutrient polymers

CMC 10: Derivative products pursuant to Regulation (EC) No. 1069/2009

	<p>CMC 11: By-products in accordance with Directive 2008/98/EC CMC 12: Precipitated phosphate salts and derivatives CMC 13: Thermal oxidation materials and derivatives CMC 14: Pyrolysis and gasification materials CMC 15: Recovered high purity materials</p> <p>The CMC 3 is the one referring to compost</p>
<p>For regulatory text:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which raw materials are allowed for the EOM production? 	<p>RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED:</p> <p>bio-waste from separate bio-waste collection at source;</p> <p>living or dead organisms or parts thereof not chemically treated with the exception of: mixed municipal wastes, sewage and industrial sludges and animal by-products within the scope of Regulation n. 1069/2009*</p> <p>any material listed above that has previously been composted and digested and contains no more than 6 mg/kg of PAH16</p> <p>composting additives (< 5% of total input material by weight)</p> <p>* Notwithstanding the ban to use animal by-products, an EU fertilising product may contain compost obtained through aerobic composting of Category 2 or Category 3 materials or derived products thereof, if specified conditions are met concerning the determination of the end point in the manufacturing chain and the process conditions</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which production process is allowed? 	<p>PRODUCTION PROCESS ALLOWED:</p> <p>Aerobic digestion</p> <p>The anaerobic digestion shall take place in a plant: where physical contacts between input and output materials are avoided, including during storage.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) that the produced EOM has to fulfil? 	<p>The aerobic digestion shall consist of controlled decomposition of biodegradable materials, which is predominantly aerobic. All parts should be moved and turned or subject to forced ventilation and have one of the following temperature profile: 70 °C ≥ 3d, 65 °C ≥ 5d, 60 °C ≥ 7d or 55 °C ≥ 14d</p> <p>CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCED EOM:</p> <p>(a) no more than 6 mg/kg dry matter of PAH 16</p> <p>(b) no more than 3* g/kg dry matter of macroscopic impurities above 2 mm in any of the following forms: glass, metal or plastics;</p> <p>(c) no more than 5 g/kg dry matter of the sum of the macroscopic impurities referred to in point (b).</p> <p>The compost shall meet at least one of the following stability criteria</p> <p>Oxygen uptake ratio: ≤ 25 mmol O₂/kg organic matter or</p> <p>self heating factor: minimum Rottegrad III (in the self-heating test, temperature increase of 30 °C max. above room temperature)</p>
<p>For incentives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is there any incentive dedicated to the production of energy associated with the EOM co-production? 	<p>NO</p>
<p>Other comments</p>	

2.1.2 What's the **European regulatory framework** about the use of EOMs in agricultural fields?

Name of the policy	Nitrates Directive – Directive n. 91/676/CEE.
Date of entry into force of the policy at EU level	12 December 1991 and published in the Official Journal of the European Communities on 31 December 1991.
Date of transposition at national level	29 April 2006.
Type of policy instrument	Regulatory
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)	Nitrates Directive lays down precise restrictions on the use of manure. The Directive aims to protect surface and groundwater from pollution by nitrates from agricultural sources (mainly fertilisers and manure). In Italy the directive has been transposed by Article 92 of Legislative Decree n. 152/2006. The Ministerial Decree n. 5046 of 25 February 2016 have complied with the Nitrates Directive. The aim of the directive is both to reduce water pollution caused directly or indirectly by nitrates of agricultural origin and to prevent any further pollution of this type. The Nitrates Directive provides for the designation of areas vulnerable to nitrate pollution of agricultural origin, the definition of the action programmes to be applied in the Vulnerable Zones for nitrates and the monitoring of both the quality status of water bodies and the implementation of the Action Programmes.
<p>For regulatory text:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there limits to the maximum applicable amounts of the EOM in specific areas (Natura 2000, Nitrate Vulnerable Zones, etc.)? • Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) of the EOM so that it can be used as soil amendment? 	<p>LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT</p> <p>YES - The Directive lays down a limit of 170 kg of manure per hectare per year in vulnerable areas.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are there some techniques of application or scheduled timelines to be respected? 	<p>CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EOM TO BE USED AS SOIL AMENDMENT:</p>
<p>For incentives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is there any incentive dedicated to the agricultural use of EOM? 	<p>No</p>
<p>Other comments</p>	<p>No</p>

EOM: Biochar

2.1.1 What's the European regulatory framework about the production of the EOM you are referring to, so that it can be used as a soil amendment?

<p>Name of the policy</p>	<p>New European Regulation on Fertilizers EU Regulation 2019:1009 NOTE: National regulations are not cancelled</p>
<p>Date of entry into force of the policy at EU level</p>	<p>Entry into force: June 5, 2019 Application: July 16, 2022 This act has been changed. Current consolidated version: 16/03/2023 It amends the Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009</p>

	It repeals the Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003.
Date of transposition at national level	Not yet transposed
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive)	Regulatory
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)	<p>This Regulation lays down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilizing products.</p> <p>It applies to EU fertilising products, excluding animal by-products, referring to substances, mixture, micro-organism or any other material with the purpose of providing the plants or mushrooms with nutrients, which are CE marked when made available on the market.</p> <p>More specifically the regulation applies to the Product Function Categories (PFCs) (Annex 1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PFC 1: Fertilizer (organic, organo-mineral, inorganic) PFC 2: Calcium and/or magnesium correctives PFC 3: Soil improvers (organic and inorganic) PFC 4: Growing substrate PFC 5: Inhibitors (nitrification and urease) PFC 6: Plant biostimulants (microbial and non-microbial) PFC 7: Physical mixture of fertilizing products (previous points 1-6) <p>An EU fertilising product shall consist solely of the component materials (CMCs) listed in Annex II:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CMC 1: Substances and mixtures based on raw material CMC 2: Plants, plant parts or plant extracts CMC 3: Compost CMC 4: Fresh crop digestate CMC 5: Digestate different from that of fresh crops CMC 6: By-products of the food industry CMC 7: Microorganisms

- CMC 8: Nutrient polymers
- CMC 9: Polymers other than nutrient polymers
- CMC 10: Derivative products pursuant to Regulation (EC) No. 1069/2009
- CMC 11: By-products in accordance with Directive 2008/98/EC
- CMC 12: Precipitated phosphate salts and derivatives
- CMC 13: Thermal oxidation materials and derivatives
- CMC 14: Pyrolysis and gasification materials
- CMC 15: Recovered high purity materials

The CMC 14 is the one referring to biochar.

For regulatory text:

- Which raw materials are allowed for the EOM production?
- Which production process is allowed?
- Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) that the produced EOM has to fulfil?

RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED:

Organic matrixes:

- living or dead organisms (or parts thereof), virgin or treated exclusively in manual, mechanical, dissolution/extraction in water modes. Exclusion of municipal waste, sewage sludge, industrial sludge, sludge from dredging, animal by-products or derivatives referred to in EC Reg. 1069/2009 *
- vegetable waste from the food industry, fibrous vegetal waste from production of pulp and paper (not chemically treated)
- residues from the production of bioethanol and biodiesel in ref. Directive 2009/28 EC (validity deadline 06/30/21: repealed with EU directive 2018/2001)
- organic waste from separate collection (Directive 2008/98/EC art 3 p. 4): organic waste from gardens, parks, households waste or restaurant and catering waste
- additives (maximum 25% of the fresh weight of the incoming material)

	<p>*Exemption: a European fertilizer may contain CMC 14 obtained from material referred to in category 2 and 3 of EC Regulation 1069/2009, e.g. derived products and by-products of animal origin: manure, carcasses, skins, horns, parts of bones of animals no longer intended for human consumption</p> <p>PRODUCTION PROCESS ALLOWED: Pyrolysis (dry or wet) and gasification: a thermochemical conversion in limited presence of oxygen at a temperature ≥ 180 °C for at least 2 seconds. Procedures for Conformity Assessment with Regulation (EU) 1009/2019 For fertilizer products containing CMC 14, a written and diagram description of production processes needs to be provided. The Quality System which the fertilizer manufacturer must implement (form D1 – Annex IV part II), must guarantee adequate resources (staff, structures, equipment), a quality system contact person, annual internal audits, registration and control of incoming materials, samples analysis every 3,000 tons or every 2 months. The quality system must be approved by a Notified Body.</p> <p>CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCED EOM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stability: H:Corg < 0.7 • Cl⁻ ≤ 30 g/kg d.m. • TI ≤ 2 mg/kg d.m. if >5% of additives • PAH16 ≤ 6 mg/kg d.m. • PCDD/F ≤ 20 ng/kg d.m. (WHO toxicity equivalents) • if a PFC contains CMC 14 and has Mn > 3.5%, the declaration of Mn content is mandatory • if a PFC contains CMC 14 the neutralization value must be declared when it is >15 (equivalent in CaO)
For incentives:	No

Is there any incentive dedicated to the production of energy associated with the EOM co-production?	
Other comments	Before international and national regulations were defined, voluntary standards were set up and still exist.

2.1.2 What's the European regulatory framework about the use of EOMs (Biochar) in agricultural fields?

Name of the policy	New European Regulation on Fertilizers EU Regulation 2019:1009
Date of entry into force of the policy at EU level	Entry into force: June 5, 2019 Application: July 16, 2022 This act has been changed. Current consolidated version: 16/03/2023 It amends the Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 It repeals the Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003.
Date of transposition at national level	Not yet transposed
Type of policy instrument	Regulatory
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)	This Regulation lays down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products. It applies to EU fertilising products as described in the table of section 2.1.1. The regulation applies to 7 Product Function Categories (PFCs) that can be composed of 15 component materials (CMCs), with biochar being the 14 th . The regulation, in the Annex II, describes the characteristics of the CMCs as described in the table of section 2.1.1. but other requirements will derive from the PFC that the CMC will be part of. It is likely that biochar will be part of PFC 3A: ORGANIC SOIL IMPROVER or PFC 4 GROWING MEDIUM. If so, the parameters to be respected are reported to answer to the next question.
For regulatory text:	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there limits to the maximum applicable amounts of the EOM in specific areas (Natura 2000, Nitrate Vulnerable Zones, etc.)? • Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) of the EOM so that it can be used as soil amendment? • Are there some techniques of application or scheduled timelines to be respected? 	<p>No</p> <p>CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EOM TO BE USED AS SOIL AMENDMENT:</p> <p>See Table 2.1.1 + EU Regulation 1009:2019 Example of other requirements depending on the PFC REQUIREMENTS FOR PFC 3A (ORGANIC SOIL AMENDMENTS)</p> <p>A. Contaminants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inorganic arsenic (As): ≤ 40 mg/kg d.m. • cadmium (Cd): ≤ 2 mg/kg d.m. • hexavalent chromium (Cr VI): ≤ 2 mg/kg d.m. • lead (Pb): ≤ 120 mg/kg d.m. • mercury (Hg): ≤ 1 mg/kg d.m. • nickel (Ni): ≤ 50 mg/kg d.m. • copper (Cu): ≤ 300 mg/kg d.m. • zinc (Zn): ≤ 800 mg/kg d.m. <p>B. Pathogens:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salmonella spp.: absent in 25 g or 25 ml (in 5 replicates) • Escherichia Coli or Enterococcaceae: ≤ 1000 CFU in 1 g or 1 ml (in 5 replicates)
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C. Other requirements:

- dry substance: $\geq 20\%$
- total organic carbon: $\geq 7.5\%$
- pH declaration – electrical conductivity, Norg and C/N

Example of other requirements depending on the **PFC REQUIREMENTS FOR PFC 4 (GROWING MEDIA)**:

A. Contaminants

- inorganic arsenic (As): ≤ 40 mg/kg d.s.
- cadmium (Cd): ≤ 2 mg/kg d.s.
- hexavalent chromium (Cr VI): ≤ 2 mg/kg d.s.
- lead (Pb): ≤ 120 mg/kg s.s.
- mercury (Hg): ≤ 1 mg/kg d.s.
- nickel (Ni): ≤ 50 mg/kg d.s.
- copper (Cu): ≤ 200 mg/kg d.s.
- zinc (Zn): ≤ 500 mg/kg d.s.

B. Other properties to declare

- pH
- electric conductivity
- N CAT (if value >150 mg/L)
- P₂O₅ CAT (if value >20 mg/L)
- K₂O CAT (if value >150 mg/L)

APPLICATION TECHNIQUES OR SCHEDULED TIMELINES

	No
	Biochar has been included in the European list of products (fertilizers, soil improvers and nutrients) authorized in organic farming (EU Executive Regulation 2019/2164 of the Commission of 17/12/2019)
For incentives: • Is there any incentive dedicated to the agricultural use of EOM?	No
Other comments	Pyrolysis and gasification material must be registered, unless expressly covered by one of the exemptions, in accordance with the REACH regulation (EC) no. 1907/2006 – Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals, in a file containing: a) the information required by Annexes VI, VII and VIII of Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006 b) a chemical safety report in accordance with Article 14 of regulation (EC) no. 1907/2006 regarding its use as a fertilizing product.

EOM: Compost

2.1.1 What's the European regulatory framework about the production of the EOM you are referring to, so that it can be used as a soil amendment?

Name of the policy	New European Regulation on Fertilizers EU Regulation 2019:1009 NOTE: National regulations are not cancelled
Date of entry into force of the policy at EU level	Entry into force: June 5, 2019 Application: July 16, 2022

[This act has been changed. Current consolidated version: 16/03/2023](#)

It amends the Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009

It repeals the Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003.

Date of transposition at national level	Not yet transposed
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive)	Regulatory
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)	<p>This Regulation lays down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilizing products.</p> <p>It applies to EU fertilising products, excluding animal by-products, referring to substances, mixture, micro-organism or any other material with the purpose of providing the plants or mushrooms with nutrients, which are CE marked when made available on the market.</p> <p>More specifically the regulation applies to the Product Function Categories (PFCs) (Annex 1):</p> <p>PFC 1: Fertilizer (organic, organo-mineral, inorganic) PFC 2: Calcium and/or magnesium correctives PFC 3: Soil improvers (organic and inorganic) PFC 4: Growing substrate PFC 5: Inhibitors (nitrification and urease) PFC 6: Plant biostimulants (microbial and non-microbial) PFC 7: Physical mixture of fertilizing products (previous points 1-6)</p> <p>An EU fertilising product shall consist solely of the component materials (CMCs) listed in Annex II: CMC 1: Substances and mixtures based on raw material CMC 2: Plants, plant parts or plant extracts CMC 3: Compost</p>

	<p>CMC 4: Fresh crop digestate CMC 5: Digestate different from that of fresh crops CMC 6: By-products of the food industry CMC 7: Microorganisms CMC 8: Nutrient polymers CMC 9: Polymers other than nutrient polymers CMC 10: Derivative products pursuant to Regulation (EC) No. 1069/2009 CMC 11: By-products in accordance with Directive 2008/98/EC CMC 12: Precipitated phosphate salts and derivatives CMC 13: Thermal oxidation materials and derivatives CMC 14: Pyrolysis and gasification materials CMC 15: Recovered high purity materials</p> <p>The CMC 3 is the one referring to compost</p>
<p>For regulatory text:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which raw materials are allowed for the EOM production? 	<p>RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED:</p> <p>bio-waste from separate bio-waste collection at source;</p> <p>living or dead organisms or parts thereof not chemically treated with the exception of: mixed municipal wastes, sewage and industrial sludges and animal by-products within the scope of Regulation n. 1069/2009*</p> <p>any material listed above that has previously been composted and digested and contains no more than 6 mk/kg of PAH16</p> <p>composting additives (< 5% of total input material by weight)</p> <p>* Notwithstanding the ban to use animal by-products, an EU fertilising product may contain compost obtained through aerobic composting of Category 2 or Category 3 materials or derived products thereof, if specified conditions are met concerning the determination of the end point in the manufacturing chain and the process conditions</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which production process is allowed? 	<p>PRODUCTION PROCESS ALLOWED:</p> <p>Aerobic composting</p> <p>The composting shall take place in a plant: where physical contacts between input and output materials are avoided, including during storage.</p> <p>The aerobic composting shall consist of controlled decomposition of biodegradable materials, which is predominantly aerobic. All parts should be moved and turned or subject to forced ventilation and have one of the following temperature profile: 70 °C ≥ 3d, 65 °C ≥ 5d, 60 °C ≥ 7d or 55 °C ≥ 14d</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) that the produced EOM has to fulfil? 	<p>CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCED EOM:</p> <p>(a) no more than 6 mg/kg dry matter of PAH 16</p> <p>(b) no more than 3* g/kg dry matter of macroscopic impurities above 2 mm in any of the following forms: glass, metal or plastics;</p> <p>(c) no more than 5 g/kg dry matter of the sum of the macroscopic impurities referred to in point (b).</p> <p>The compost shall meet at least one of the following stability criteria</p> <p>Oxygen uptake ratio: ≤ 25 mmol O₂/kg organic matter or</p> <p>self heating factor: minimum Rottegrad III (in the self-heating test, temperature increase of 30 °C max. above room temperature)</p>
<p>For incentives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is there any incentive dedicated to the production of 	<p>No</p>

energy associated with the EOM co-production?	
Other comments	

2.1.2 What's the European regulatory framework about the use of EOMs (compost) in agricultural fields?

Name of the policy	New European Regulation on Fertilizers EU Regulation 2019:1009	Nitrates Directive – Directive n. 91/676/CEE.
Date of entry into force of the policy at EU level	Entry into force: June 5, 2019 Application: July 16, 2022 This act has been changed. Current consolidated version: 16/03/2023 It amends the Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 It repeals the Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003.	12 December 1991 and published in the Official Journal of the European Communities on 31 December 1991.
Date of transposition at national level	Not yet transposed	29 April 2006
Type of policy instrument	Regulatory	Regulatory
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)	This Regulation lays down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products. It applies to EU fertilising products as described in the table of section 2.1.1. The regulation applies to 7 Product Function Categories (PFCs) that can be composed of 15 component materials (CMCs), with compost being the 3rd. The regulation, in the Annex II, describes the characteristics of the CMCs as described in the table of section 2.1.1. but other requirements will derive from the PFC that the CMC will be part of. It is likely that compost will be part of PFC 3A: ORGANIC SOIL IMPROVER or PFC 4 GROWING MEDIUM. If so, the parameters to be respected are reported to answer to the next question.	The aim of the Directive is to protect surface and groundwater from pollution by nitrates from agricultural sources (mainly fertilisers and livestock manure). The Italian law transposing the Nitrates Directive is Legislative Decree no. 152 of 3 April 2006, Article 92. The aim of the Directive is both to reduce water pollution caused directly or indirectly by nitrates of agricultural origin and to prevent any further pollution of this type. It provides for the designation of areas vulnerable to nitrate pollution of agricultural origin, the definition of the action programmes to be applied in the Vulnerable Zones for nitrates and the monitoring of both the quality status of water bodies and the implementation of the Action Programmes. Ministerial Decree no. 5046 of 25 February 2016 is the reference standard for the adoption of Action Programmes.
For regulatory text:	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT

• Are there limits to the maximum applicable amounts of the EOM in specific areas (Natura 2000, Nitrate Vulnerable Zones, etc.)?

• Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) of the EOM so that it can be used as soil amendment?

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EOM TO BE USED AS SOIL AMENDMENT:

EU Regulation 1009:2019

Example of other requirements depending on the PFC **REQUIREMENTS FOR PFC 3A (ORGANIC SOIL AMENDMENTS)**

A. Contaminants:

- cadmium (Cd): ≤ 2 mg/kg d.m.
- hexavalent chromium (Cr VI): ≤ 2 mg/kg d.m.
- lead (Pb): ≤ 120 mg/kg d.m.
- mercury (Hg): ≤ 1 mg/kg d.m.
- nickel (Ni): ≤ 50 mg/kg d.m.
- copper (Cu): ≤ 300 mg/kg d.m.
- zinc (Zn): ≤ 800 mg/kg d.m.
- inorganic arsenic (As): ≤ 40 mg/kg d.m.

In Nitrate Vulnerable Zones total amount of efficient N supplied with compost must not exceed the crop's requirements calculated with a nitrogen balance considering all N supplies to the crop

B. Pathogens:

- Salmonella spp.: absent in 25 g or 25 ml (in 5 replicates)
- Escherichia Coli or Enterococcaceae (in 1 g or 1 ml): $n = 5$; $c = 5$; $m = 0$;

$M = 1000$ CFU

n = number of samples to be examined; c = number of samples for which the bacterial count may be between m and M

m = threshold value for the number of bacteria; M = maximum value for the number of bacteria

C. Other requirements:

- dry substance: $\geq 20\%$
- total organic carbon: $\geq 7.5\%$
- declaration of dry matter content, N, P_2O_5 and K_2O (if exceeding 0.5%), pH, electrical conductivity, Norg and C/N

Example of other requirements depending on the **PFC REQUIREMENTS FOR PFC 4 (GROWING MEDIA)**:

A. Contaminants

- cadmium (Cd): ≤ 1.5 mg/kg d.m.
- hexavalent chromium (Cr VI): ≤ 2 mg/kg d.m.
- lead (Pb): ≤ 120 mg/kg d.m.
- mercury (Hg): ≤ 1 mg/kg d.m.
- nickel (Ni): ≤ 50 mg/kg d.m.
- copper (Cu): ≤ 200 mg/kg d.m.
- zinc (Zn): ≤ 500 mg/kg d.m.
- inorganic arsenic (As): ≤ 40 mg/kg d.m.

B. Pathogens:

- Salmonella spp.: absent in 25 g or 25 ml (in 5 replicates)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Escherichia Coli or Enterococcaceae (in 1 g or 1 ml): n = 5; c = 5; m = 0; M= 1000 CFU <i>n = number of samples to be examined; c = number of samples for which the bacterial count may be between m and M</i> <i>m = threshold value for the number of bacteria; M = maximum value for the number of bacteria</i> <p>C. Other properties to declare</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • electric conductivity • pH • quantity (size) • N CAT (if value >150 mg/L) • P₂O₅ CAT (if value >20 mg/L) • K₂O CAT (if value >150 mg/L) <p>Compost has been included in the European list of products (fertilizers, soil improvers and nutrients) authorized in organic farming (EU Executive Regulation 2019/2164 of the Commission of 17/12/2019). It has to fulfil the following requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - product obtained from source-separated household waste that is composted or anaerobically fermented to produce biogas - only if produced within a closed and supervised collection system - contaminants maximum concentrations (mg/kg dm): Cd: 0.7; Cu: 70; Ni: 25; Pb: 45; Zn: 200; Hg: 0.4; Cr (total): 70; Cr(VI): not detectable 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there some techniques of application or scheduled timelines to be respected? 		<p>In area vulnerable to nitrates there is a temporary ban to compost application (90 days, from 15 November to 15 February), except from compost with less than 2.5% total N and maximum 15% of NH₄⁺-N that is banned from 15 December to 15 January). Also, compost must be applied</p>

		beyond a determined distance from water bodies. For the use of organic soil improvers (manure and compost), no specific constraints are set regarding the time of their distribution and fractioning. They must, however, be incorporated into the soil and sanitary and hygiene regulations must be respected.
For incentives: •Is there any incentive dedicated to the agricultural use of EOM?	No	No
Other comments	European Commission has listed compost as an exempt substance under the REACH chemical regulations (Regulation (EC) N. 1907/2006, Annex V)	

2. Results from questionnaire at European and National level

General information coming from questionnaires

Partners participating to the survey in the countries which are part of the EOM4SOIL consortium are: (Italy, France, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Lithuania, Sweden, Austria, Spain, Switzerland and Türkiye). (IT, FR, BE, DN, FI, LT, SE, AU, SP, SW, TK).

Investigating compliance with the new European regulation on fertilizers

The conformity assessment requires a good quality management and assurance system covering the production and the products, as already implemented in 11 European countries/regions (EEA, 2020).

Investigating compliance with Animal By-Products as fertilizers

For EU Fertilising products of component material categories which include animal byproducts (e.g., catering waste, digestate, manure) as defined in the Animal By-Products Regulation (EU) No 1069/2009 the end point of the manufacturing chain for animal by-products has to be reached and the process requirements of both regulations (ABPR and FPR) should apply cumulatively to EU fertilising products. For compost and digestate the end point in the manufacturing chain is laid down in Regulation (EU) 2023/1605. This regulation determines end points in the manufacturing chain for organic fertilisers and soil improvers manufactured in the EU beyond which they are no longer subject to the ABPR, if they are used as component materials in EU fertilising products in accordance with the FPR.

National and European threshold values for contaminants in EOM' amendments

The quality standards for heavy metals and impurities and the limits on application doses to soil vary between countries/regions, as they are mostly dependent on the specific situation, for example the soil structure, background concentrations of pollutants, agricultural practices, and lack or presence of other soil improvers/fertilisers (Saveyn et al., 2014).

A survey conducted by the European Environment Information and Observation Network (Eionet) in 2019 (Eionet, 2019) revealed that 24 European countries have national standards for compost quality, which are either set in legislation, standalone standards or under development. In some countries/regions, including Flanders (Belgium), existing national standards are more stringent than the EU soil improver standards for compost based on bio-waste and garden waste (EEA, 2020).

Process requirements and conformity assessment in EOM' amendments

The final fertilising products can be placed on the market according to a specific conformity assessment procedure laid down in the FPR. Rules apply to the certification at both PFC and CMC level. If compost or digestate from waste materials are used in an organic fertiliser, soil improver or growing media, an external conformity assessment – including process and

product control – by a notified body is mandatory. Regulation for biochar production and use is well defined.

Process requirements and conformity assessment in EOM' amendments – organic production regulation

Regulation (EU) 2018/848 is the current legal act establishing obligations for organic production and labelling of organic products (REGULATION (EU) 2018/848 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL, 2018). The new Organic Regulation is the result of a long revision process that involved the repealing of the previous regulation on organic production and labelling together with other various implementing acts. Obligations on the authorisation of fertilisers, soil improvers and nutrients in organic production are set in art. 24. These products and substances can be accepted when they are essential for building up and maintaining fertility of the soils or fulfilling specific nutritional requirements of crops. In this regard, Annex II of Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/1165 (2021), respecting the correcting Regulation (EU) 2023/2229 adopted on 25 October 2023, establishes a list of these products and substances while setting further requirements for their authorisation and use in organic production. Compost and digestate produced from household waste figure among the materials accepted, followed by specifications and conditions for their application. These conditions include feedstock materials, production requirements and limit values for contaminants. Contamination limits of heavy metals for compost and digestate used in organic farming are stricter than the ones laid down in the FPR.

Specific information coming from questionnaires for digestate, biochar, compost

Digestate

1. European Regulatory Framework on EOMs

The European Union has established a harmonized regulatory framework through the European Fertilising Products Regulation (EU 2019/1009). This regulation, effective since July 16, 2022, governs the marketing of fertilizing products in the EU, including organic fertilizers, soil improvers, and growing media. It defines 15 Component Material Categories (CMCs), with digestate falling into the following CMCs: CMC 4: Fresh crop digestate and CMC 5: Digestate other than fresh crop digestate.

2. Comparison with National Regulations

2.1. Italy

Italy has transposed the European framework into national law through the Decree of 25 February 2016, n. 5046, concerning the “General technical criteria and standards for the regional regulation of the agronomic use of livestock effluents and wastewater, as well as for the production and agronomic use of digestate” of the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies.

The Decree, which serves as the reference legislation for the adoption of Action Programmes defined under the Nitrates Directive, establishes the general criteria and technical rules for the agricultural use of digestate. It also regulates the quality characteristics of digestate.

Firstly, the Italian framework aligns with the European requirements by specifying raw materials and production processes.

Pursuant to articles 22 to 34, digestate used for agronomic use must derive from anaerobic digestion systems fed by materials used either alone or mixed together, such as straw, mowing and pruning residues, as well as other non-hazardous agricultural materials pursuant to Article 185, paragraph 1, letter f) of Legislative Decree n. 152/2006; agricultural materials derived from dedicated agricultural crops; livestock effluents; sewage; vegetation waters of the oil mills and wet pomace in accordance with Law n. 574/1996; agri-food residues; and animal by-products used in compliance with EC Regulation n. 1069/2009, as well as agricultural and forestry materials not intended for human consumption as identified in Table 1B of the Ministerial Decree of 6 July 2012.

Agro-industrial digestate can be produced by the anaerobic digestion plant fed with sewage, residues from agri-food activities and animal by-products. These materials must come from: agricultural or agri-food activities carried out by the same firm managing or owning the plant, or from agricultural or agri-food firms that are associated or associated with the interfarm plant; an agricultural or agri-food production process of which they are an integral part and be used to feed the anaerobic digestion plant. Finally, these materials must not be dangerous or polluted.

Digestate and agro-industrial digestate cannot be produced by anaerobic digestion plants fed with grass cuttings or other plant material used for the safety or remediation of contaminated sites, and with grass cuttings or other material coming from land used for food crop production.

Differences:

The Italian regulation makes no mention of either algae or additives.

- In Italy specific incentives have been established. Decree-Law 228/21 extended incentives from 2021 to 2022 for entrepreneurs operating biogas plants with a maximum power of 300 kw. The incentive was granted if the plants were fed at least 80% by livestock manure and materials mainly derived from farms themselves, with the remaining 20% coming from second harvest crops.

Subsequently, the Decree 15 September 2022 of the Ministry of the Ecological transition defined new incentives for biomethane under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan - NRRP (measure '*Development of biomethane, according to criteria for the promotion of the circular economy- ecological practices*', Mission 2, Component 2, Investment 1.4). The measure allocates EUR 1.92 billion for the development of biomethane and the promotion

and dissemination of ecological practices in the biogas production. This goal is to reduce the use of synthetic fertilisers, increase soil organic matter, and create consortia for centralised digestate treatment with the production of organic fertilisers. The first public calls for the construction of new biomethane plants or for the conversion of existing biogas plants were launched in 2023.

Digestate used for agronomic purposes is excluded from waste regulations, as it is considered a by-product. The maximum amount of digestate that can be applied to soil depends on the area. Similar to effluents, the agronomic use of digestate must comply with the nitrogen limit in the field of 170 kg per hectare per year in nitrate-vulnerable areas and 340 kg per hectare per year in non-vulnerable areas. The percentage of digestate coming from the digestion of non-zootechnical materials must be included in the nitrogen balance for agronomic use. Digestate may be used as soil amendment if it complies with certain parameters regarding Corg, Pb, Cd, Cu, Zn, Ni, N, Hg, Cr VI.

- The use of digestate is relatively simple, since it can be applied directly to the soil without further treatment than normal practices such as dehydration, sedimentation, clarification, centrifugation and drying, filtration, solid-liquid separation, stripping, nitrification, denitrification and phytoremediation.

Other Comments

Dried digestate has been included among the marketable nitrogenous fluid organic fertilizers under Legislative Decree n. 75/2010 (updated with the Decree-Law of 1 March 2022, concerning “Urgent measures for the containment of electricity and natural gas costs, the development of renewable energies and the revitalisation of industrial policies”).

2.3. Netherlands

The Dutch regulatory framework for digestate is structured through the following pieces of legislation: the Implementation Regulations of the Fertilisers Act (uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet), the Environmental Activities Decree (Besluit activiteiten leefomgeving), and the Environmental Quality Decree.

The first regulation establishes limits for N and P that can be applied; in addition, Annex Aa of the regulation provides a list of waste materials and associated production processes permitted for the use of digestate as a fertiliser or co-digestion material (along with manure). The national legislation lay down practical rules, such as when certain fertilisers can be used.

Differences:

- In the Netherlands, energy production and CO₂-reducing techniques are subsidised under the Subsidy Sustainable Energy Production and Climate Transition (SDE++). This has relevant

implications to produce renewable gas and digestate. The subsidy is available to companies and organisations (excluding the national government). For digestate, at least 50% of the input should be animal manure.

- Regarding the use of digestate in specific areas, Implementation Regulations of the Fertilisers Act (uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet) sets limits for N and P application. The N application requirement depends on the crop and the use of catch crops, and whether the area is designed as a groundwater protection area or nutrient pollution zone. The P application requirement depends on the soil status and whether the land is arable or grassland. In addition, maximum values for heavy metals and arsenic are set in Table 1 and Table 4 of Annex II of the Implementation Regulations of the Fertilisers Act. Finally, digestate, like other fertilisers other than animal manure, may not contain degradable particles larger than 50 mm, and may not contain more than 0.5% non-degradable parts (stones etc).

2.4. Belgium

Similar to Italy and the Netherlands, Belgium follows a regulatory approach. The primary reference is the Royal Decree of January 28, 2013, which covers the marketing and use of fertilisers, soil improvers, and growing substrates. The decree outlines rules regarding composition, labelling, marketing, and use of these products, aiming to protect public health, the environment, and promote sustainable agriculture.

Differences:

Digestate must meet specific quality standards in Belgium, specifically regarding the content of cadmium, chromium, organic matter, mercury, nickel, plumb, zinc, and cobalt.

Belgium does not offer specific incentives for the agricultural use of digestate.

2.5. Lithuania

The regulatory reference for digestate is the Order of the Ministry of Environment No. D1-57 (25 January 2007), which outlines environmental requirements for composting and anaerobic treatment of biodegradable waste. The current version, updated on May 1, 2023, sets key conditions for managing biodegradable waste through composting and anaerobic processes.

Differences:

The regulation specifies the types of waste that can be composted or treated anaerobically, including non-hazardous biodegradable waste such as:

- Food waste from public catering, kitchens, and food production and trade facilities.
- Biodegradable waste separately collected from households or other sources.
- Green waste like branches, grass, leaves, and flowers.
- Non-hazardous agricultural waste and residues such as straw, potato, and sugar beet leaves.

- Biodegradable waste from non-hazardous wood processing and other production activities.
- Recycled wastepaper and cardboard, excluding materials coated with non-biodegradable substances.

The regulation also sets criteria for the raw materials, including:

- Maximum allowable concentrations of heavy metals (Cr, Cd, Hg, Pb, Ni, As, Cu, Zn).
- Biological safety requirements (e.g., helminth eggs and larvae, salmonella presence).
- Physical contamination limits (e.g., glass, metals, and plastics larger than 2 mm).
- Limits of unwanted materials like germinated plant seeds, viable weeds, rhizomes, and stones larger than 10 mm.

Specific criteria are defined for the use of digestate as a fertilizer in specific areas. Limits are set for nitrogen (170 kg/ha per year), phosphorus (40 kg/ha per year) or phosphorus pentoxide (P₂O₅) (90 kg/ha per year).

2.6. Walloon

The Decree of the Walloon Government of 24 April 2014 laying down the sectoral conditions relating to biomethanisation installations focuses on the production conditions for biogas through biomethanisation, specifying the types and minimum quality standards of input materials. The law ensures compliance with strict standards to promote safe and efficient biogas production. It does not include guidelines for the use of digestate on soils.

The raw materials permitted for biomethanisation include energy crops and waste products. Specifically:

1 Only non-hazardous biomaterials are permitted in biomethanisation and in post-treatment processes.

2 Biomaterials entering the biomethanisation process, i.e., wastewater treatment plant sludge and livestock effluents, must comply with the specific legislation. Livestock effluents require a land application contract between the producing farm and the biomethanisation plant operator.

The biomaterials used in the biomethanisation process and the materials used in the post-treatment process must have concentrations of trace metallic elements (TMEs) below certain limits. They must contain less than 0.2 per cent by weight of impurities such as glass, plastic and metal, and less than 2 per cent by weight of stones.

The Walloon law PGDA (*Programme de Gestion Durable de l'Azote*) aims to regulate and mitigate the impacts of nitrogen use on the environment, particularly water pollution and air quality issues. It includes provisions such as limits on nitrogen fertilizer application, requirements for livestock effluent management, incentives for adopting more sustainable farming practices to reduce nitrogen leaching and other forms of pollution. The primary goal

is to promote more responsible nitrogen use in agriculture to safeguard ecosystem health and human populations.

Differences

The production process allowed is the anaerobic biological mesophilic digestion.

The legislation provides strict criteria for the chemical composition of raw materials, with reference to concentrations of heavy metals such as Cr, Cd, Cu, Hg, Pb, Ni, and Zn.

Specific limits are set for organic nitrogen inputs when using digestate as a fertilizer in specific areas: across the entire farm's utilized agricultural area, as well as on a given plot, the average amount of organic nitrogen inputs may not exceed 115 Kg/ha per year for arable land or 230 kg/ha per year for grassland. In vulnerable zones, organic nitrogen inputs may not exceed an average of 170 kg/ha.

3. Other Comments

- In Belgium, the digestate produced has to meet certain quality requirements (heavy metal content), while in Lithuania and Wallonia, the focus is on the raw material characteristics.
- In Italy, the Netherlands, Lithuania and Wallonia, specific limits are set for the use of digestate as fertiliser in certain areas.
- Only Italy and the Netherlands have incentive schemes for the production of energy from digestate. Other countries do not report specific incentives as highlighted in the EU context.
- Italy and Lithuania are examples of countries where a lot of attention is paid to non-hazardous biodegradable waste that can be treated anaerobically.

These discrepancies highlight the need for further regulatory harmonization and incentives to promote the greater use of digestate, with particular attention to sustainability and environmental protection.

References

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3. Biochar

1. European Regulatory Framework on EOMs

The European Union has established a harmonized regulatory framework through the European Fertilising Products Regulation (EU 2019/1009). This regulation, effective since July 16, 2022, governs the marketing of fertilizing products in the EU, including organic fertilizers, soil improvers, and growing media such as biochar. It defines seven functional categories (PFCs) of fertilizing products and 15 component materials (CMCs), with biochar primarily classified in PFC 3A (Organic Soil Improvers) or PFC 4 (Growing Media).

2. Comparison with National Regulations

2.1. Italy

Italy has transposed the European framework with specific national regulations, including:

- Ministerial Decree of June 22, 2015, which includes biochar as a "soil improver" within national fertilizer legislation (Lgs. D. no. 75/2010).
- Ministerial Decree of October 10, 2022, which includes biochar among the fertilizers used in organic farming.

The Italian framework aligns with European requirements regarding permitted raw materials, production processes (pyrolysis and gasification), and the physical and chemical characteristics of biochar. However, some differences emerge in the limits for contaminants such as lead, cadmium, and zinc, which are stricter than the European parameters.

Differences:

- The limits for Lead and Mercury are slightly higher at the European level.
- There are no specific incentives for the agricultural application of EOMs in Italy, consistent with EU regulations.

2.2. Netherlands

The Dutch regulatory framework is outlined through the Fertiliser Act (meststoffenwet) and various implementing regulations (Uitvoeringsbesluit, Uitvoeringsregeling). In the Netherlands, biochar produced from waste is not yet regulated as an EOM since there has been no request from companies. However, biochar made from non-waste materials can be used as an organic fertilizer if composition requirements are met.

Differences:

- Biochar from waste: It is not yet allowed under Dutch national regulations, while the EU accepts it under specific restrictions.
- Dutch phosphorus application norms in agricultural fields are more detailed than EU requirements, including additional parameters for phosphorus and groundwater management.

2.3. Belgium

Belgium follows a regulatory approach with the Royal Decree of January 28, 2013, which covers the marketing and use of fertilizers, soil improvers, and growing media. Permitted raw materials include woody plants, and the allowed production process is pyrolysis.

Belgian regulatory parameters generally align with European standards but show some discrepancies in the limits for heavy metals such as lead and zinc, which are slightly lower than those in EU regulations. However, there are no specific incentives for the agricultural application of EOMs.

2.4. Finland

Finland has a clear regulatory framework with the Decree of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry on Fertiliser Products (964/2023), which allows the production of fertilizers until the end of 2024. Additionally, Finland promotes the use of recycled fertilizers through the Nutrient Recycling Scheme, an incentive program supporting the use of biogas and digestate-based fertilizers.

Differences:

- Finland has an incentive scheme for recycled fertilizers, promoting the use of digestates and biogas-based fertilizing products, which is not included in the EU framework.
- Finnish regulation focuses more on creating a market for recycled fertilizers, positively impacting the use of EOMs.

2.5. Lithuania

Lithuania does not have a specific national regulation for the use of biochar as an EOM. The regulation of fertilizers is still largely based on European regulations, and there is no detailed information on raw materials, production processes, or chemical characteristics of EOM products. There are also no incentives for the agricultural application of EOMs.

Differences:

- Lack of specific regulation for biochar as an EOM, contrasting with countries like Italy, Belgium, and Finland, which have already established clear national rules.
- No comparable data on permitted raw materials, production processes, or contaminant limits.

3. Other Comments

- Integration between EU and national regulations: Most member states closely follow the European regulatory framework, with some exceptions regarding contaminant limits or specific raw materials (Netherlands, Belgium).
- Incentive systems: Finland is the only country among those analysed with a dedicated incentive system promoting recycled fertilizers. Other countries do not report specific incentives, as highlighted in the EU context.
- Lack of national regulations: Lithuania represents a case where no consolidated regulation for biochar or other EOMs exists, which may limit the adoption of these technologies within the country.

These discrepancies highlight the need for further regulatory harmonization and incentives to promote the greater use of EOMs, with particular attention to sustainability and environmental protection.

The comparison reveals that while some countries (like Italy and Belgium) are closely aligned with the EU's standards for EOM characteristics, other nations (such as Finland, the Netherlands, and Lithuania) show significant regulatory gaps. This highlights the need for

further harmonization across the EU, particularly in areas such as biochar stability, chlorine content, and specific pollutant limits (e.g., thallium, PAHs). Countries with fewer regulations or incomplete frameworks, like Lithuania, might need to adopt more comprehensive standards to ensure alignment with the EU's environmental and agricultural goals.

3.5 Compost

Italy

According to the Italian Legislation (Fertiliser Law, D.Lgs 75/2010 and subsequent amendments) compost, which is classified as a soil improver and is divided into four categories depending on the type of feedstock material:

- GW (green) Compost: compost produced from GW only;
- BW (browns) Compost: compost produced from BW, including both food- and GW;
- Sludge Compost: compost produced including sludge inside the mixture of different feedstock.
- Compost from waste from the agri-food chain: compost produced from digestate of agro-industrial sludge, wastewater and agro-industrial sludge, animal waste, and GW (Ministero delle politiche agricole alimentari e forestali, 2022).

The Italian standard for end-of-waste compost established in the Fertilisers Law comprises agronomical parameters (pH, moisture content, carbon and organic nitrogen, etc.), environmental parameters (heavy metals and physical impurities), as well as sanitisation parameters (Salmonella, E. Coli) (CIC, 2021).

Austria

The Compost Ordinance of 2001, which is currently under revision, sets up quality requirements for compost produced from waste. Requirements regulate the production, marketing and labelling of compost as a product, meaning that also end-of-waste criteria are established. It includes requirements regarding compost designation and specification, waste materials (waste codes) with approved origin, type and frequency of quality measurements for certain feedstock materials, as well as type and schedule of records and documentation. The ordinance classifies compost into three different quality-based categories and defines raw feedstock materials accepted for each one of them. The three classes, built around the heavy metals content of the finished compost, are: ' +' meaning top quality, which is accepted in organic farming; '' which stands for high quality and is suitable for agricultural use; and finally, '' for minimum quality, applied in non-agricultural contexts. Moreover, Austria has in place a series of national standards and guidelines establishing requirements for a quality assurance scheme for compost. In Austria, digestate produced from organic residues is considered waste until proper recovery in the soil, according to the Waste Management Act 2002.

Belgium

Belgium is divided into three regions – Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels – and waste policy falls under regional jurisdiction (Vlaco, 2023). The Flemish region is the only one which has in place quality standards for compost and digestate, therefore only Flanders will be considered for the purpose of this guideline. The reference legislation is the VLAREMA regulation which contains requirements for the use of treated BW as a secondary raw material (fertiliser or soil improver) and describes all the requisites for the certification of compost and digestate products. VLAREMA sets up limit values for the most important environmental parameters, both organic (e.g., PAH, PCB, other organic compounds) and inorganic (e.g., heavy metals).

Germany

In Germany, two different ordinances are relevant for compost and digestate quality standards. The revised Bio-waste Ordinance (BioAbfV) published in 2022 regulates the application of treated and untreated BW and mixtures in and on soils (Kleine Novelle Der Bioabfallverordnung (BioAbfV), 2022). It also covers suitable raw materials, quality and hygiene requirements, and treatment and investigations of such BW and mixtures. The Biowaste Ordinance regulates – from a precautionary perspective – the waste side (e.g. heavy metals) of the application, whereas the fertiliser law regulates the nutrient part. The Fertiliser Law (Düngeverordnung (DüV), 2017) sets the frame for the good practice of fertilising and shows special requirements for organic fertilisers. It includes the restrictions for the application of fertilisers with essential nutrient contents in winter periods and restricts the application of organic fertilisers to an average of 170 kg N/ha. In addition, compost and digestate have to be declared in accordance with the German Fertiliser Ordinance (Düngemittelverordnung (DüMV), 2019). A declaration of the fertiliser type, raw material, nutrients and other product properties is obligatory. Threshold values for impurities or contaminants like PFT, PCCD or dlPCB, included in the Fertiliser Ordinance are obligatory for compost and digestate, too.

Spain

Catalonia has no comprehensive QAS in place but has set up a specific strategy to improve the quality of the feedstock materials.

Estonia

Estonia has end-of-waste regulation for compost and digestate in place. In 2013 the regulation “Requirements for producing compost from biodegradable waste” was enforced in Estonia. The ordinance regulates and sets requirements for the production site, production technology and limit values for various parameters. In 2016 the regulation “Requirements for biogas digestate generated from biodegradable waste” was enforced in Estonia. These regulations function as end-of-waste legislation, enabling producers of compost and digestate generated from biodegradable waste to certify compost and digestate as a product. Based on the manual of the ECN-QAS Estonia has set up a quality assurance scheme for compost and digestate. This QAS is owned by the Certification Centre of Recycled Materials which has been accredited

according to ISO/IEC 17065 as a certification body for compost and digestate quality assurance since 2016.

Finland

Products from organic waste are sold as fertilizers for agriculture or landscaping and under the supervision of the Finnish Plant Production Inspection Centre. According to the Finnish legislation, only officially certified products can be put on the market. The certified products are controlled on a regular basis for pathogens, heavy metals and nutrients. Based on the manual of the ECN-QAS, Finland has developed a quality assurance scheme for compost and digestate which is owned by the Biocycle and Biogas Association.

France

Based on the manual of the ECN-QAS France has developed a quality assurance scheme for compost which is owned by Réseau Compost Plus (label Amendement Sélectionné Qualité Attestée - ASQA). The ASQA foresees a three-years audit cycle. During the first year one preparatory and one complete audit are performed, followed by a surveillance audit in the second year and a renewal audit during the last one.

Netherlands

Product quality standards for compost in the Netherlands are specified in the Fertiliser decree accompanying the Fertiliser law. Minimum content of organic matter is set at 10% DM and limit values for heavy metal contamination are outlined. The standards also set limitations for physical impurities. Furthermore, it exists a voluntary standard called "Keurcompost" which goes beyond the limits and thresholds legally established, setting stricter requirements which are verified by third party audits and accredited auditors. Keurcompost requirements are on processing (temperature-time and sanitisation), quality management, and on impurities standards in compost differentiated between glass, stones and others; two categories are defined, differing in terms of limit values for impurities (Keurkompost, 2023). This standard is executed jointly by BVOR and DWMA, the Dutch Bio-waste Management Association and Dutch Waste Management Association, respectively (BVOR, 2023).

3.6 Suitable feedstock to produce soil amendments from EOMs: EOMs in agriculture

Feedstock suitable to produce compost and digestate should always originate from source-separate and/or agricultural residues and food waste from industries that have not been mixed, combined or contaminated with other potentially polluting waste, to ensure the highest purity from the beginning of the recycling system. Information on the source of waste shall be available to assess its suitability and to meet the product quality criteria for compost and digestate. Mixed municipal waste is excluded as feedstock material for quality compost and digestate. Dedicated quality assurance schemes include a positive list of feedstock materials. The visual feedstock control and the documentation of the feedstock materials is a pre-requisite for a good operation process. Furthermore, a waste composition analysis can be applied to identify the detailed waste composition intended for biological treatment.

Compost, biochar and digestate have different uses because of their intrinsic characteristics, which are in turn a direct effect of the type of feedstock used in composting and digestion plants or in pyrolysis process for biochar production.

3. Concluding remarks

Due to the increasing volume of organic wastes from urban, industrial and agricultural entities, the use of EOMs for as soil amendment is of extreme importance. Infact, the use and application of EOMs (e.g., animal manures, biochar, digestate, compost, etc..) is increasing worldwide, which can be used as a source of exogenous organic matter for soil. The soil application of EOMs as amendments has been proposed as an effective way of restoring degraded soils, while at the same time, protecting the environment as their use could be part of a strategy to eliminate massive amounts of sub products. This is particularly relevant in the current attempts to reach a fully circular economy, which advocates for capturing and reusing organic wastes.

Considering political recommendation, advancements in the sector must be led by the European Commission and will require cross-examining modalities and the inclusion of multi-disciplinary expertise. EOMs management necessitates concerted coordination across MS in legal, environmental, political, fiscal, organizational, technical, and communication areas. This report's findings suggest that a multitude of barriers plague the European institutions and stakeholders struggling to meet the EU mandate for separate collection of EOMs and the landfill and recycling targets, thereby precluding the closure of the circular economy. The core lines of action to improve the production in terms of (quantity and quality and use) of EOMs managed include:

- Close the gaps in and advance the regulatory framework,
- Promote and align economic incentives and funding,
- Extend the network of expert stakeholders across all levels of governance,
- Improve technical know-how and validation of BPs,
- Increase communications, public education and awareness, • Implement efficient and individualised models (that identifies the user and allows controls of the collected material) and monitor performance.

4. Lessons learned and main messages

This section concludes from the previous descriptions and summarises important steps to promote high quality compost and digestate.

- High-quality feedstock material eases the production of high-quality products.

- Pre- and post-treatment is important for improving the quality of and refining the final product.
- Know benefits of anaerobic digestion and composting as well as their combination. Be aware of local circumstances and technical potentials for treatment to select a preferred treatment pathway as well as the required capacity. Consider the principle of proximity when planning the location of the treatment plant.
- Best practice cases showcase that with different type of technology, similar products can be obtained. However, advanced processes can deal with lower quality of input material.
- Get informed with EU legislation and the national legislation is inappropriately developed.
- Requirement to implement a national body that develops or adapts standards as well as high-quality compost, biochar and digestate.
- Countries with a fully developed quality standard and QAS also produce the highest quality of compost.
- Know about the different market sectors that may require different specifications for compost and digestate.
- Be aware of the fertiliser market and the marketing potentials with composts and digestate from different feedstock materials and with different product qualities that may be suitable for different end uses. The continuous production of high-quality compost, biochar and digestate will increase the acceptance of the customers and create a higher value on the market as compared to non-quality assured products.
- In contrast to mineral fertilisers, digestate and especially compost and biochar or both have positive long-term properties on soil health and stability in addition to the fertilising properties. These benefits shall be communicated to promote the use of high-quality compost and digestate to farmers and other end users to increase their acceptance.

ANNEX I EU policy framework influencing the production and use of EOM' amendments (Waste Framework Directive)

The European research project External organic matters for climate mitigation and soil health (EOM4SOIL) funded by the European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management (EJP SOIL) aims at proposing best management practices of external organic matter (EOM) pre-processing and application to agricultural soils to contribute to climate change mitigation and improve soil health.

The present survey refers to manure, slurry, compost, sewage sludge, digestate and biochar and has the aim to: i) evaluate the current European and national regulatory framework about their production and use in soils and to ii) identify the regulatory obstacles that hamper the value chain development (both from the production and use perspectives)

In same specific case, compost coming from FORSU (organic municipal waste) or (urban green waste and pruning) is important also to consider the Waste Framework Directive (WFD).

While EU waste legislation is commendable in its scope and comprehension, measures related to bio-waste recycling are not uniformly implemented within and across all Member States (MS). In some areas, bio-waste management is nascent. The vast majority of EU MS, regrettably, do not fully comply with the 2024 obligation of separate collection across all its *municipalities*. While collection systems may exist, the capture and the quality of separately collected material must be improved, especially for food waste. The Waste Framework Directive (WFD) directly target biowaste management and exist within a multitude of cross-cutting policy legislation, demonstrating that bio-waste management has wide reaching implications and can be a driver of many sectorial policies.

This report's findings suggest that a multitude of barriers plague the European institutions and stakeholders struggling to meet the EU mandate for separate collection of bio-waste and the landfill and recycling targets, thereby precluding the closure of the bio-waste cycle. Many barriers are interrelated and dispersed across EU MS, necessitating multiple transversal and vertical solutions to overcome them. Additionally, this study investigates the status of transposition and management results of the EU legal framework and proposes calls to action.

Some administrative barriers common aspects coming out from survey:

- EU - Lack of quality standards for input materials
- EU - Environmental and/or agricultural policies and management protocols lack synergies
- National - Competition between recycling of and energy recovery from biowaste
- National - Regulatory uncertainty or modifications lead to highly variable systems
- Regional - Administrative and bureaucratic barriers to implement / improve the treatment units

Economic Barriers

- National - lack of guidance on use of EU funds
- National - Low costs of landfilling or low/lack of tariffs
- National - Low costs of incineration or low/lack of tariffs
- Regional - Lack or uncertainties regarding financing/subsidies for treatment
- Municipal - Lack of resources to build or outfit waste treatment facilities for biowaste

ANNEX II. Barriers to the development of the production and use value-chain of EOMs

2.2.3 Are there other policy instruments, in your country, which can have an indirect impact on the use of EOMs in agricultural soils?

The answer reported in this section are referred to Italy.

Name of the policy instruments	Type (regulatory, incentive, agreement)	General scope	Impact on EOMS use in agricultural fields
NEC directive - directive UE n. 2016/2284.	Regulatory.	Reduce ammonia volatilisation and improve air quality through sustainable soil intake management techniques of digestate and effluent (direct injection, burial, precision agriculture) and storage tank cover	Management of the storage and spreading of manure and digestate.
IED directive - Directive UE n. 2010/75	Regulatory.	It regulates industrial emissions, makes the granting of permits for industrial installations subject to the best available techniques (BAT-Best Available Techniques) and has the objective of avoiding or minimising pollutant emissions into the atmosphere, in water and soil, as well as waste from industrial and agricultural installations	The zootechnical activities subject to the Integrated Environmental Authorisation (AIA) are those concerning intensive livestock farming of poultry and pigs with 40,000 or more places, 2,000 pig places for production of more than 30 kg and/or 750 sows places.

3.1 Which gaps and barriers do you see in the current European legislation about the production of EOMs?

EOMs	Gaps in the current European legislation	Barriers in the current European legislation
Biochar		
Digestate	There is no legislation on digestate production.	

Compost	Lack of regulations favouring on site composting (farm composting)	Legislation promoting alternative use of organic waste (i.e. bioenergy). Lack of harmonisation between European and national legislation
Other...		

3.2 Which gaps and barriers do you see in the current European legislation about the application of EOMS in agricultural fields?

EOM	Gaps in the current European legislation	Barriers in the current European legislation
Biochar	<p>Impossibility of commercialization of digestate as fertilizer as not foreseen in Lgs. D. no. 75/2010. It is currently transferable to third parties free of charge.</p> <p>The non-application of the regulation on digestate equivalent to fertilizers pursuant to Article 21 of Decree - Law No. 21 of 21 March 2022, converted, with amendments, by Law No. 51 of 20 May 2022.</p>	
Digestate	The non-application of the regulation on digestate equivalent to fertilizers pursuant to Article 21 of Decree - Law n. 21 of 21 March 2022, converted, with amendments, by Law n. 51 of 20 May 2022.	
Compost	Classification of compost based on use (e.g. agriculture, horticulture, growing media) rather than on feedstocks used for composting would give to the farmers a better idea of the offered compost quality and its characteristics favouring its application.	Contradictory legislation promoting compost application on one side (Mid-Term Review of the Common Agricultural Policy (COM/2002/0394)) and limiting it on the other side (fertilization legislation, e.g. Nitrate Directive).
Other...		

3.3 Is the value chain well-known and well-developed by relevant stakeholders in your country?

EOM	Well-known value chain (Yes/No)	Well-developed value chain (Yes/No) - Why?
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Biochar	Yes	Yes, for agronomic application and no for marketing.
Digestate	Yes and in the regions located in northern Italy.	Yes for agronomic application and no for marketing.
Compost	Yes	No, quality of compost can be improved. The market value of compost is low with respect to production costs
Other...		

3.4 Can EOMs be commercialized as fertilizers/amendments in your country?

EOM	Commercialized as fertilizer (Yes/No)
Biochar	NO, it is possible to transfer it to third parties free of charge.
Digestate	It is possible to transfer it to third parties free of charge. Some types of digestate are permitted as fertilizers pursuant to Legislative Decree. n. 75/2010. The European Fertilizer Regulation provides for the use as fertilizer of digestate coming from solid organic waste (FORSU) and plant biomass.
Compost	The compost can be commercialised as fertilizer pursuant to Legislative Decree. n. 75/2010.
Other...	

Source: our elaboration from CREA on various references from partners investigations.

ANNEX III. Questionnaire, digestate, biochar and compost at EU and MS level (production and use value-chain of EOMs)

2.2.3.1 Description of the EU policy framework influencing the production and use of EOM' amendments

2.1. Digestate

2.1.1 What's the European regulatory framework about the production of EOMs that can be used as soil amendments?

2.1.2 What's the European regulatory framework about the use of EOMs in agricultural fields?	
Name of the policy	Nitrates Directive – Directive n. 91/676/CEE.
Date of entry into force of the policy at EU level	12 December 1991 and published in the Official Journal of the European Communities on 31 December 1991.
Date of transposition at national level	29 April 2006
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive)	Regulatory
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)	<p>Nitrates Directive lays down precise restrictions on the use of manure. The Directive aims to protect surface and groundwater from pollution by nitrates from agricultural sources (mainly fertilisers and manure). In Italy the directive has been transposed by Article 92 of Legislative Decree n. 152/2006. The Ministerial Decree n. 5046 of 25 February 2016 have complied with the Nitrates Directive.</p> <p>The aim of the directive is both to reduce water pollution caused directly or indirectly by nitrates of agricultural origin and to prevent any further pollution of this type.</p> <p>The Nitrates Directive provides for the designation of areas vulnerable to nitrate pollution of agricultural origin, the definition of the action programmes to be applied in the Vulnerable Zones for nitrates and the</p>

	monitoring of both the quality status of water bodies and the implementation of the Action Programmes.
For regulatory text: Are there limits to the maximum applicable amounts of the EOM in specific areas (Natura 2000, Nitrate Vulnerable Zones, etc.)?	IMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT: YES - The Directive lays down a limit of 170 kg of manure per hectare per year in vulnerable areas.
Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) of the EOM so that it can be used as soil amendment?	
For incentives: Is there any incentive dedicated to the production of energy associated with the EOM co-production?	No
Other comments	No

2.2.1 Which is the national regulatory framework of your country about the production of EOMs, if different from the European regulations reported in the previous section 2.1?

Country	Italy	Finland	Nederland	Belgium	Lithuania	Waloon
Name of the policy	Ministerial Decree 25 February 2016, n. 5046 which has "General technical criteria and standards for the regional regulation of the agronomic use of livestock effluents and wastewater, as well as for the		Fertilizer Implementing regulation (uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet), and the Environmental activities decree (Besluit activiteiten leefomgeving)	JANUARY 28, 2013. - Royal Decree on the marketing and use of fertilizers, soil improvers and growing substrates.	Ministry of Environment of the Republic of Lithuania order 25 January 2007, No. D1-57 "Approval of environmental requirements for composting and anaerobic treatment of biological waste"	April 24, 2014 - Walloon Government decree determining the sectoral conditions relating to biomethanization installations covered by heading 90.23.15 and amending the Walloon Government decree of July 4, 2002 relating to the procedure and various measures for

	production and agronomic use of digestate					implementing the decree of March 11, 1999 relating to environmental permits (M.B. 24.06.2014)
Date of entry into force	25 February 2016			Published in the Moniteur Belge on March 13, 2013	22 February 2007 published in "Valstybės žinios" the official publication of legal acts of the Republic of Lithuania, No. 23-902. Valid from 23 February 2007, Current summary version of the order 01 May 2023.	Published in the Moniteur Belge on June, 24, 2014.
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive, agreement)	Regulatory		Regulatory		Regulatory	Regulatory
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)	Ministerial Decree n. 5046 of 25 February 2016 represents the reference legislation for the adoption of the Action Programmes defined pursuant to the Nitrates Directive.		The Implementing regulation gives limits to the amount of applied N and P (§ 3 Uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet). The Environmental activities decree, and Environmental quality decree lays down more practical rules, such as when you are allowed to use certain fertilisers.	This Royal Decree, dated January 28, 2013, pertains to the marketing and use of fertilizers, soil amendments, and cultivation substrates in Belgium. Its objective is to regulate these products to ensure	The environmental requirements for composting and anaerobic treatment of biodegradable waste determine the conditions for composting and anaerobic treatment of biodegradable waste, the types of waste to be composted and anaerobically treated,	This Wallonian decree establishes specific regulations for biomethanization installations categorized under 90.23.15. It primarily focuses on production conditions for biogas through biomethanization and stipulates the permitted types and minimum

	<p>The decree n. 5046 repealing the Ministerial Decree of 7 April 2006. The Decree lays down the criteria and general technical rules for the agricultural use of manure, sewage and digestate in order to enable the nutrients and soil improvers contained therein to play a useful role on agricultural soil, achieving a conciliatory, soil improver, irrigation, fertigation or corrective effect on the land subject to agricultural use, in accordance with the quantitative and temporal</p>			<p>their quality, safety, and compliance with established standards. The decree establishes rules regarding the composition, labeling, marketing, and utilization of these products, aiming to protect public health, the environment, and promote sustainable agriculture.</p>	<p>requirements for the quality, contamination and use of compost, anaerobic ferment, classification of compost, anaerobic ferment criteria for fertilizing products</p>	<p>quality standards of input materials. The law ensures adherence to stringent operational standards aimed at promoting safe and efficient biogas production. Notably, it does not include directives regarding the utilization of digestate on soils, but rather emphasizes requirements for the production phase of biomethanization.</p>
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	requirements of the crops. The rule is integrated with the application of the provisions of Part Three of Legislative Decree No. 152/2006.					
For regulatory text: Which raw materials are allowed for the EOM production?	RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED: The digestate used for agronomic use must derive (pursuant to article 22 of Ministerial Decree no. 5046 "Production of digestate") from anaerobic digestion systems fed by materials, whether used alone or mixed together, such as straw , mowing and pruning as well as other non-		RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED: In case of waste materials, there is a list of permitted materials and processes for use as fertiliser or for use as codigestion material (with manure): Appendix Aa of the regulation (bijlage Aa Uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet).		RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED: The following non-hazardous biodegradable waste can be anaerobically treated: food waste generated in public catering establishments and kitchens, including public and household kitchens, food production and trade establishments, unsuitable food products that have become waste; separately collected biological waste generated in the household or other sources, when its composition is identical to the biological waste	RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED: "The raw materials authorised for biomethanisation are energy crops and a range of waste products that meet the criteria below. § 1 Only biomaterials considered to be non-hazardous in accordance with the decree of 10 July 1997 establishing a catalogue of waste and its amendments are permitted in biomethanisation. Only materials considered to be non-hazardous in accordance with the

<p>dangerous agricultural material pursuant to article 185, paragraph 1, letter f) of Legislative Decree n. 152/2006; agricultural material deriving from dedicated agricultural crops; from livestock effluents; from sewage; from the vegetation waters of the oil mills and humid pomace in accordance with Law n. 574/1996; residues agri-food activity; from animal by-products used in compliance with the provisions of EC Regulation n. 1069/2009 and from agricultural and forestry material not</p>				<p>generated in the household, or separated (sorted) biodegradable waste from the mixed municipal waste stream; green waste (for example, branches, grass, leaves of trees, bushes, flowers); natural non-hazardous agricultural, horticultural waste, residues (for example, straw, potatoes, sugar beet leaves); non-hazardous wood processing waste; non-hazardous biodegradable waste from production and other economic activities; recycle waste paper and cardboard (except paper and cardboard waste covered with a non-biodegradable coating material).</p>	<p>decree of 10 July 1997 establishing a waste catalogue and its amendments are permitted in post-treatment. § 2 The biomaterials entering the biomethanisation process and the materials used in the post-treatment process have concentrations of trace metallic elements, referred to as "TMEs", below the following limit values: see below*" "§ 3 Wastewater treatment plant sludge used in biomethanisation has a certificate of use issued on the basis of the Walloon Government Decree of 12 January 1995 regulating the use on or in the soil of wastewater treatment plant sludge or sludge from septic tank sludge treatment centres. § 4 Livestock effluents accepted for</p>
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<p>intended for human consumption identified in table 1B of the Ministerial Decree of 6 July 2012. The agro-industrial digestate is produced by the anaerobic digestion plant fed by sewage, residues from agri-food activities, vegetation water from oil mills and wet pomace, and animal by-products. Such materials must originate from agricultural or agri-food activities carried out by the same undertaking that has the management or ownership of the plant or come</p>					<p>biomethanisation are the subject of a land application contract, as defined by Chapter IV of Book II of the Environmental Code, containing the Water Code, between the farm that generates them and the operator of the biomethanisation facility. § 5 The biomaterials used in biomethanisation and the materials used in post-treatment contain less than 0.2 percent by weight of impurities such as glass, plastic and metal. If this is technically impossible, the biomethanisation installation will be equipped with a refining installation enabling the finished product to comply with this standard. § 8. Les additifs améliorent la biométhanisation sans détériorer la qualité du digestat. § 9. Les biomatières entrant dans la</p>
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<p>from agricultural or agri-food enterprises associated or associated with the interfarm plant; originate from an agricultural or agri-food production process of which they form an integral part, and be used to feed the anaerobic digestion plant. Finally, these substances must not be dangerous or polluted. Digestate and agro-industrial digestate cannot be produced by anaerobic digestion plants fed by grass cuttings or other plant material used for the safety</p>					<p>biométhanisation et les matières utilisées dans le post-traitement ne peuvent pas contenir de contaminants en quantité telle qu'elle risque de compromettre la biométhanisation, la filière de valorisation ou d'élimination du digestat. § 6 The biomaterials used in biomethanisation and the materials used in post-treatment contain less than 2 percent by weight of stones. If this is technically impossible, the biomethanisation installation will be equipped with a refining installation enabling the finished product to comply with this standard. § 7 The wood used in biomethanisation is untreated. § 8. Les additifs améliorent la biométhanisation sans détériorer la qualité du digestat.</p>
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	or remediation operations of contaminated sites and by grass cuttings or other material coming from land intended for the production of food crops.					§ 9. Les biomatières entrant dans la biométhanisation et les matières utilisées dans le post-traitement ne peuvent pas contenir de contaminants en quantité telle qu'elle risque de compromettre la biométhanisation, la filière de valorisation ou d'élimination du digestat."
Which production process is allowed?			In case of waste materials: this is different per material. See: bijlage Aa Uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet			PRODUCTION PROCESS ALLOWED: Anaerobic biological mesophilic digestion
Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) that the produced EOM has to fulfill?				CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCED EOM: PRODUCED EOM [mg/kg of dry matter] Substantial qualities whose content must be guaranteed Cadmium 2,5 Chrome 100	CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RAW MATERIALS: Parameter Lithuania regulation value Cr, mg/kg d.m. ≤70 Cd, mg/kg d.m. ≤2 Hg, mg/kg d.m. ≤1.0 Pb, mg/kg d.m. ≤120 Ni, mg/kg d.m. ≤50 As, mg/kg d.m. ≤40 Cu, mg/kg d.m. ≤300 Zn, mg/kg d.m. ≤800 Escherichia coli ≤1000 CFU/g	CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RAW MATERIALS: *RAW MATERIALS [mg/kg of dry matter] Cadmium 5 Chrome 500 Cuivre 600 Mercure 5 Nickel 100 Plomb 500 Zinc 2000

				Organic matter : minimum 10% Cuivre 250 Mercure 2,5 Nickel 50 Plomb 500 Zinc 750 Cobalt 10	Clostridium perfringens ≤100 000 CFU/g Helminth eggs and larvae 0 unit/g Salmonella spp 0 unit/g Glass, metals, plastic, when their particles are larger than 2 mm, % ≤0.5 Germinated plant seeds, including viable weeds, rhizomes, unit/kg ≤2 Stones larger than 10 mm in dry weight, % ≤5	
For incentives: Is there any incentive dedicated to the production of energy associated with the EOM co-production?	Yes The DL 228/21 (Budget Law 2019) provided for the extension of incentives for Biogas Plants from 2021 to 2022. In detail, it encourages the creation by entrepreneurs of electricity production plants powered by biogas with a maximum power of 300 kw.		Yes, energy production is subsidised, which is relevant for digestate. In digestate at least 50% of the input should be animal manure (bijlage Aa Uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet), or 0%. https://english.rvo.nl/subsidies-financing/sde/apply	No	No	No

	<p>The incentive is granted if the plants are fed at least 80% by livestock manure and materials mainly derived from the same farms and the remaining 20% from second harvest crops. In 2023 the first public calls for the construction of new biomethane plants or for the conversion of the biogas plant pursuant to DM 15/09/2022 that defines the new incentives for biomethane were launched. Companies to access the calls must submit the title of authorization to the construction</p>					
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	<p>and operation of the plant valid and effective, the estimate of connection to the network accepted (in case of connection to the network with obligation to connect to third parties), the certificate of conformity of sustainability of biofuels and bioliquids as defined by DM 14/11/2019 and the certificate of greenhouse gas savings specific to the intended use of biomethane. In addition, the companies must have the digestate storage tanks covered with biogas recovery</p>					
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<p>for a volume of 30 days. During the construction of the biomethane plant, the producer must have documentation to demonstrate the traceability of biomass and its traceability. The National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) for the agriculture sector, it envisages an investment of EUR 1.92 billion for the measure on the development of biomethane and the promotion and dissemination of ecological practices in the biogas production phase in order to reduce the use of</p>					
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	<p>synthetic fertilisers, increase the supply of organic matter in the soils and create poly consortiums for the centralized treatment of digestate and effluents with production of fertilizers of organic origin. The measure aims to promote innovation and diversification of agricultural enterprises and contributes to combating climate change and improving air quality by reducing the volatilisation of ammonia</p>					
Other comments	<p>Possibility of selling it as fertilizer pursuant</p>					

	to Legislative Decree n. 75/2010. The dried digestate has been included among the nitrogenous fluid organic fertilizers pursuant to Legislative Decree n. 75/2010 (updated with the legislative decree of 1 March 2022 of the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies - published in the Official Journal n. 108 of 10 May 2022).					
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2.2.2 Which is the national regulatory framework of your country about the use of EOMs in agricultural fields, if different from the European regulations reported in the previous section 2.1?

Country	Italy	Finland	Nederland	Belgium	Lithuania	Waloon
Name of the policy	Ministerial Decree 25 February 2016, n. 5046 which has		Fertilizer Implementing regulation (uitvoeringsregeling	JANUARY 28, 2013. - Royal Decree on the	Ministry of Environment of the	Sustainable Nitrogen Management Program (PGDA, version IV: Walloon Government Order of February 23, 2023, published on April 05, 2023)

	"General technical criteria and standards for the regional regulation of the agronomic use of livestock effluents and waste water, as well as for the production and agronomic use of digestate		Meststoffenwet), and the Environmental activities decree (Besluit activiteiten leefomgeving)	marketing and use of fertilizers, soil improvers and growing substrates.	Republic of Lithuania order 25 January 2007, No. D1-57 "Approval of environmental requirements for composting and anaerobic treatment of biological waste"	
Date of entry into force	25 February 2016					
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive, agreement)	Regulatory		Regulatory	Regulatory	Regulatory	Regulatory
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)	Ministerial Decree n. 5046 of 25 February 2016 represents the reference legislation for the adoption of the Action		The Implementing regulation gives limits to the amount of applied N and P (§ 3 Uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet). The Environmental activities decree, and	This Royal Decree, dated January 28, 2013, pertains to the marketing and use of fertilizers, soil amendments, and cultivation substrates in	The environmental requirements for composting and anaerobic treatment of biodegradable	The Walloon law PGDA (Programme de Gestion Durable de l'Azote) aims to regulate and mitigate the impacts of nitrogen use on the environment, particularly water pollution and air quality issues. It includes provisions such as limits on nitrogen fertilizer application, requirements for livestock effluent management, incentives for adopting more sustainable farming practices to reduce nitrogen leaching and

<p>Programmes defined pursuant to the Nitrates Directive. The decree n. 5046 repealing the Ministerial Decree of 7 April 2006. The Decree lays down the criteria and general technical rules for the agricultural use of manure, sewage and digestate in order to enable the nutrients and soil improvers contained therein to play a useful role on agricultural soil, achieving a conciliatory, soil improver, irrigation, fertigation or corrective effect on the land subject to agricultural use, in accordance with the quantitative</p>		<p>Environmental quality decree lays down more practical rules, such as when you are allowed to use certain fertilisers.</p>	<p>Belgium. Its objective is to regulate these products to ensure their quality, safety, and compliance with established standards. The decree establishes rules regarding the composition, labeling, marketing, and utilization of these products, aiming to protect public health, the environment, and promote sustainable agriculture.</p>	<p>waste determine the conditions for composting and anaerobic treatment of biodegradable waste, the types of waste to be composted and anaerobically treated, requirements for the quality, contamination and use of compost, anaerobic ferment, classification of compost, anaerobic ferment criteria for fertilizing products</p>	<p>other forms of pollution. The primary goal is to promote more responsible nitrogen use in agriculture to safeguard ecosystem health and human populations.</p>
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	and temporal requirements of the crops. The rule is integrated with the application of the provisions of Part Three of Legislative Decree No. 152/2006.					
For regulatory text: Are there limits to the maximum applicable amounts of the EOM in specific areas (Natura 2000, Nitrate Vulnerable Zones, etc.)?	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT For the use of digestate it is necessary to focus attention on articles 22 to 34 of Ministerial Decree n. 5046. The digestate used for agronomic purposes pursuant to this decree is excluded from the application of the waste regulations as it is considered a by-product.	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT The application norms on the basis of N and P. Fertilizer Implementing regulation (uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet). Application norm for P depends on P soil status, and if arable or grassland. Application norm for N depends on crop, use of catchcrop, and is decreased if soil has a certain status as: groundwaterprotection area, nutrient pollutants area	No	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT: The maximum rate of anaerobic fermentation used must ensure that the following does not enter the soil: nitrogen - more than 170 kg/ha per year, phosphorus - 40 kg/ha or phosphorus	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT Art.R.207. Without prejudice to compliance with article R.214, § 1, organic nitrogen inputs may not exceed an average of 115 kg per hectare of arable land and an average of 230 kg per hectare of grassland, including returns to the soil by grazing animals, over one year and for the entire declared agricultural area of the farm, depending on whether it is arable land or grassland. Art. R.208. § 1 . On a given parcel of land, and without prejudice to compliance with article R.207, organic fertilizers are applied in proportions such that, over the two to seven successive years during which the plot is farmed either as arable land or grassland, depending on the rotation used, the average amount of organic nitrogen applied in any one year does not exceed: 1° 115 kg per hectare of arable land; 2° 230 kg per hectare of grassland.	

<p>Limitations are foreseen for the contribution of digestate and effluents to the soil based on the designation of the area. The agronomic use of effluents must comply with the annual nitrogen limit of 170 kg per hectare in areas vulnerable to nitrates and 340 kg per hectare per year in non-vulnerable areas. The agronomic use of digestate (article 26 of Ministerial Decree no. 5046) and agrozootechnical digestate (article 28 and 29 of Ministerial Decree n. 5046) must respect the nitrogen limit in</p>		<p>(paragraph 28 of Uitvoeringsregeling meststoffenwet).</p>		<p>(V) oxide (P2O5) - 90 kg/ha per year</p>	<p>§ 2 The maximum organic nitrogen input per plot, over one year, is set at 230 kg Norg. per hectare." Art. R.214. § 1. In vulnerable zones, over one year and for the whole of the farm's utilized agricultural area, organic nitrogen inputs to the farm's relevant areas may not exceed an average of 170 kg per hectare of utilized agricultural area.</p>
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	<p>the field of 170 kg per hectare per year in areas vulnerable to nitrates and 340 kg per hectare per year in non-vulnerable ones. The percentage of digestate coming from the digestion of non-zootechnical materials must be counted in the nitrogen balance to be reported in the agronomic use. The agronomic use of manure and digestate shall be prohibited:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - for 90 days, with the exception of bovine manure, sheep and goats and equidae, for which the regions may also provide for application in the winter months, 					
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<p>except in the period between 15 December and 15 January when used on pastures, permanent or alternating grassland and in the pre- pre-fieldplanting of horticultural crops;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 90 days in the case of manure-assimilated materials, with the exception of poultrymeat dehydrated by a rapid process with a dry matter content exceeding 65% for which the prohibition is 120 days; - for manure and similar substances 90 days in soils with grassland, cereal-autumn-winter, vegetable 					
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	<p>crops, tree crops with permanent grassing or with crop residues and in preparation for early spring sowing; and 120 days in land destined for other types of cultivation;</p> <p>- for a continuous period of at least 60 days from 1 December to 31 January of each year.</p> <p>The application of manure shall be prohibited within 25 metres of water bodies located in wetlands defined by the Ramsar Convention.</p>					
<p>Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) of</p>	<p>Parameter</p> <p>Corg (% d.m.)</p> <p>Pb (mg/kg d.s.)</p> <p>Cd (mg/kg d.s.)</p>		<p>There are limit values for other organic fertilisers (other than animal manure)</p>	<p>CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCED EOM:</p>	<p>Parameter Lithuania regulation value:</p>	

<p>the EOM so that it can be used as soil amendment?</p>	<p>Cu (mg/kg d.s.) Zn (mg/kg d.s.) Ni (mg/kg d.s.) N (mg/kg d.s.) Hg (mg/kg d.s.) Cr VI (mg/kg d.s.)</p>		<p>Artikel 15 Uitvoeringsbesluit Meststoffenwet the norms for digestate are given in Table 1, and Table 4. Bijlage II Uitvoeringsbesluit Meststoffenwet There are no norms for animal manure or slurry. Other organic fertilisers (other than animal manure) may not contain degradable particles larger than 50 mm and may not contain more than 0.5% non-degradable parts (stones etc). Artikel 13 Uitvoeringsbesluit Meststoffenwet</p>	<p>PRODUCED EOM [mg/kg of dry matter] Substantial qualities whose content must be guaranteed Cadmium 2,5 Chrome 100 Organic matter: minimum 10% Cuivre 250 Mercure 2,5 Nickel 50 Plomb 500 Zinc 750 Cobalt 10</p>	<p>Cr, mg/kg d.m. ≤70 Cd, mg/kg d.m. ≤2 Hg, mg/kg d.m. ≤1.0 Pb, mg/kg d.m. ≤120 Ni, mg/kg d.m. ≤50 As, mg/kg d.m. ≤40 Cu, mg/kg d.m. ≤300 Zn, mg/kg d.m. ≤800 Escherichia coli ≤1000 CFU/g Clostridium perfringens ≤100 000 CFU/g Helminth eggs and larvae 0 unit/g Salmonella spp 0 unit/g Glass, metals, plastic, when their particles</p>	
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					are larger than 2 mm, % ≤0.5 Germinated plant seeds, including viable weeds, rhizomes, unit/kg ≤2 Stones larger than 10 mm in dry weight, % ≤5	
Are there some techniques of application or scheduled timelines to be respected?			Yes, article 4.1184 t/m 4.1192 from Environmental activities decree (Besluit activiteiten leefomgeving).			APPLICATION TECHNIQUES OR SCHEDULED TIMELINES "See spreading calendar, page 3 https://www.protecteau.be/sites/default/files/2024-02/PE_FeuilletPGDAIV_%28275x390%292402_01_0.pdf "
For incentives: Is there any incentive dedicated to the agricultural application of the EOM?	Digestate can be applied directly to the soil without further treatment than normal practices such as dehydration, sedimentation, clarification, centrifugation and drying, filtration,		Yes The P application norm depends on soil P status AND is higher for certain types of organic-rich fertilizer. This enables farmers that have fields with low soil organic matter levels, to use more straw-rich			No

	<p>solid-liquid separation, stripping, nitrification, denitrification and phytoremediation. The application of manure on agricultural soil requires treatment operations.</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>The DL 228/21 (Budget Law 2019) provided for the extension of incentives for Biogas Plants from 2021 to 2022. In detail, it encourages the creation by entrepreneurs of electricity production plants powered by biogas with a maximum power of 300 kw. The incentive is granted if the plants are fed at</p>		<p>manures, solid-fraction of manure, chompost.</p>			
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<p>least 80% by livestock manure and materials mainly derived from the same farms and the remaining 20% from second harvest crops. In 2023 the first public calls for the construction of new biomethane plants or for the conversion of the biogas plant pursuant to DM 15/09/2022 that defines the new incentives for biomethane were launched. Companies to access the calls must submit the title of authorization to the construction and operation of the plant valid and effective, the</p>					
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	<p>estimate of connection to the network accepted (in case of connection to the network with obligation to connect to third parties), the certificate of conformity of sustainability of biofuels and bioliquids as defined by DM 14/11/2019 and the certificate of greenhouse gas savings specific to the intended use of biomethane. In addition, the companies must have the digestate storage tanks covered with biogas recovery for a volume of 30 days. During the construction of the</p>					
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	<p>biomethane plant, the producer must have documentation to demonstrate the traceability of biomass and its traceability. The National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) for the agriculture sector, it envisages an investment of EUR 1.92 billion for the measure on the development of biomethane and the promotion and dissemination of ecological practices in the biogas production phase in order to reduce the use of synthetic fertilisers, increase the supply of organic matter in the soils and create</p>					
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	poly consortiums for the centralized treatment of digestate and effluents with production of fertilizers of organic origin. The measure aims to promote innovation and diversification of agricultural enterprises and contributes to combating climate change and improving air quality by reducing the volatilisation of ammonia					
Other comments	Possibility of selling it as fertilizer pursuant to Legislative Decree n. 75/2010. The dried digestate has been included among the nitrogenous fluid organic fertilizers		Types of fertiliser for which a higher P application norm is allowed: Artikel 33b Uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet			

	<p>pursuant to Legislative Decree n. 75/2010 (updated with the legislative decree of 1 March 2022 of the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies - published in the Official Journal n. 108 of 10 May 2022).</p>					
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2.2.3.1 Description of the EU policy framework influencing the production and use of EOM' amendments

2.2.3.1.1. Biochar

2.1 What's the European regulatory framework about the production of EOMs that can be used as soil amendments?	
Name of the policy	New European Regulation on Fertilizers EU Regulation 2019:1009 NOTE: National regulations are not cancelled
Date of entry into force of the policy at EU level	Entry into force: June 5, 2019 Application: July 16, 2022 This act has been changed. Current consolidated version: 16/03/2023 It amends the Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 It repeals the Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003.
Date of transposition at national level	Not yet transposed
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive)	Regulatory
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)	This Regulation lays down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilizing products. It applies to EU fertilising products, excluding animal by-products, referring to substances, mixture, micro- organism or any other material with the purpose of providing the plants or mushrooms with nutrients, which are CE marked when made available on the market. More specifically the regulation applies to the Product Function Categories (PFCs) (Annex 1): PFC 1: Fertilizer (organic, organo-mineral, inorganic) PFC 2: Calcium and/or magnesium correctives PFC 3: Soil improvers (organic and inorganic) PFC 4: Growing substrate PFC 5: Inhibitors (nitrification and urease) PFC 6: Plant biostimulants (microbial and non-microbial) PFC 7: Physical mixture of fertilizing products (previous points 1-6)

	<p>An EU fertilising product shall consist solely of the component materials (CMCs) listed in Annex II:</p> <p>CMC 1: Substances and mixtures based on raw material CMC 2: Plants, plant parts or plant extracts CMC 3: Compost CMC 4: Fresh crop digestate CMC 5: Digestate different from that of fresh crops CMC 6: By-products of the food industry CMC 7: Microorganisms CMC 8: Nutrient polymers CMC 9: Polymers other than nutrient polymers CMC 10: Derivative products pursuant to Regulation (EC) No. 1069/2009 CMC 11: By-products in accordance with Directive 2008/98/EC CMC 12: Precipitated phosphate salts and derivatives CMC 13: Thermal oxidation materials and derivatives CMC 14: Pyrolysis and gasification materials CMC 15: Recovered high purity materials</p> <p>The CMC 14 is the one referring to biochar.</p>
<p>For regulatory text: Which raw materials are allowed for the EOM production?</p>	<p>RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED:</p> <p>Organic matrixes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •living or dead organisms (or parts thereof), virgin or treated exclusively in manual, mechanical, dissolution/extraction in water modes. Exclusion of municipal waste, sewage sludge, industrial sludge, sludge from dredging, animal by-products or derivatives referred to in EC Reg. 1069/2009 * •vegetable waste from the food industry, fibrous vegetal waste from production of pulp and paper (not chemically treated) •residues from the production of bioethanol and biodiesel in ref. Directive 2009/28 EC (validity deadline 06/30/21: repealed with EU directive 2018/2001)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •organic waste from separate collection (Directive 2008/98/EC art 3 p. 4): organic waste from gardens, parks, households waste or restaurant and catering waste •additives (maximum 25% of the fresh weight of the incoming material) <p>*Exemption: a European fertilizer may contain CMC 14 obtained from material referred to in category 2 and 3 of EC Regulation 1069/2009, e.g. derived products and by-products of animal origin: manure, carcasses, skins, horns, parts of bones of animals no longer intended for human consumption</p>
<p>Which production process is allowed?</p>	<p>Pyrolysis (dry or wet) and gasification: a thermochemical conversion in limited presence of oxygen at a temperature ≥ 180 °C for at least 2 seconds. Procedures for Conformity Assessment with Regulation (EU) 1009/2019 For fertilizer products containing CMC 14, a written and diagram description of production processes needs to be provided. The Quality System which the fertilizer manufacturer must implement (form D1 – Annex IV part II), must guarantee adequate resources (staff, structures, equipment), a quality system contact person, annual internal audits, registration and control of incoming materials, samples analysis every 3,000 tons or every 2 months. The quality system must be approved by a Notified Body.</p>
<p>Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) of the EOM so that it can be used as soil amendment?</p>	<p>CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCED EOM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stability: H:Corg < 0.7 • Cl- ≤ 30 g/kg d.m. • TI ≤ 2 mg/kg d.m. if >5% of additives • PAH16 ≤ 6 mg/kg d.m. • PCDD/F ≤ 20 ng/kg d.m. (WHO toxicity equivalents) • if a PFC contains CMC 14 and has Mn > 3.5%, the declaration of Mn content is mandatory • if a PFC contains CMC 14 the neutralization value must be declared when it is >15 (equivalent in CaO)

For incentives: Is there any incentive dedicated to the production of energy associated with the EOM co-production?	No
Other comments	Before international and national regulations were defined, voluntary standards were set up and still exist.

2.2 What's the European regulatory framework about the use of EOMs in agricultural fields?	
Name of the policy	New European Regulation on Fertilizers EU Regulation 2019:1009
Date of entry into force of the policy at EU level	Entry into force: June 5, 2019 Application: July 16, 2022 This act has been changed. Current consolidated version: 16/03/2023 It amends the Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 It repeals the Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003.
Date of transposition at national level	Not yet transposed
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive)	Regulatory
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)	This Regulation lays down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products. It applies to EU fertilising products as described in the table of section 2.1.1. The regulation applies to 7 Product Function Categories (PFCs) that can be composed of 15 component materials (CMCs), with biochar being the 14th. The regulation, in the Annex II, describes the characteristics of the CMCs as described in the table of section 2.1.1. but other requirements will derive from the PFC that the CMC will be part of.

	It is likely that biochar will be part of PFC 3A: ORGANIC SOIL IMPROVER or PFC 4 GROWING MEDIUM. If so, the parameters to be respected are reported to answer to the next question.
For regulatory text: Are there limits to the maximum applicable amounts of the EOM in specific areas (Natura 2000, Nitrate Vulnerable Zones, etc.)?	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT No
Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) of the EOM so that it can be used as soil amendment?	CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EOM TO BE USED AS SOIL AMENDMENT: See Table 2.1.1 + EU Regulation 1009:2019 Example of other requirements depending on the PFC REQUIREMENTS FOR PFC 3A (ORGANIC SOIL AMENDMENTS) A. Contaminants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •inorganic arsenic (As): ≤ 40 mg/kg d.m. •cadmium (Cd): ≤ 2 mg/kg d.m. •hexavalent chromium (Cr VI): ≤ 2 mg/kg d.m. •lead (Pb): ≤ 120 mg/kg d.m. •mercury (Hg): ≤ 1 mg/kg d.m. •nickel (Ni): ≤ 50 mg/kg d.m. •copper (Cu): ≤ 300 mg/kg d.m. •zinc (Zn): ≤ 800 mg/kg d.m. B. Pathogens: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Salmonella spp.: absent in 25 g or 25 ml (in 5 replicates) •Escherichia Coli or Enterococcaceae: ≤ 1000 CFU in 1 g or 1 ml (in 5 replicates) C. Other requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •dry substance: ≥ 20% •total organic carbon: ≥ 7.5% •pH declaration – electrical conductivity, Norg and C/N

	<p>Example of other requirements depending on the PFC REQUIREMENTS FOR PFC 4 (GROWING MEDIA):</p> <p>A. Contaminants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inorganic arsenic (As): ≤ 40 mg/kg d.s. • cadmium (Cd): ≤ 2 mg/kg d.s. • hexavalent chromium (Cr VI): ≤ 2 mg/kg d.s. • lead (Pb): ≤ 120 mg/kg s.s. • mercury (Hg): ≤ 1 mg/kg d.s. • nickel (Ni): ≤ 50 mg/kg d.s. • copper (Cu): ≤ 200 mg/kg d.s. • zinc (Zn): ≤ 500 mg/kg d.s. <p>B. Other properties to declare</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pH • electric conductivity • N CAT (if value >150 mg/L) • P2O5 CAT (if value >20 mg/L) • K2O CAT (if value >150 mg/L) <p>APPLICATION TECHNIQUES OR SCHEDULED TIMELINES No</p> <p>Biochar has been included in the European list of products (fertilizers, soil improvers and nutrients) authorized in organic farming (EU Executive Regulation 2019/2164 of the Commission of 17/12/2019)</p>
<p>Are there some techniques of application or scheduled timelines to be respected?</p>	<p>APPLICATION TECHNIQUES OR SCHEDULED TIMELINES No</p>

	Biochar has been included in the European list of products (fertilizers, soil improvers and nutrients) authorized in organic farming (EU Executive Regulation 2019/2164 of the Commission of 17/12/2019)
For incentives: • Is there any incentive dedicated to the production of energy associated with the EOM co-production?	No
Other comments	Pyrolysis and gasification material must be registered, unless expressly covered by one of the exemptions, in accordance with the REACH regulation (EC) no. 1907/2006 – Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals, in a file containing: a) the information required by Annexes VI, VII and VIII of Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006 b) a chemical safety report in accordance with Article 14 of regulation (EC) no. 1907/2006 regarding its use as a fertilizing product.

2.2.1 Which is the national regulatory framework of your country about the production of EOMs, if different from the European regulations reported in the previous section 2.1?

Country	Italy	Finland	Nederland	Belgium	Lithuania	Wallonia
Name of the policy	The Ministerial Decree 06/22/2015 (GU 186 of	The regulation is in force under the Fertiliser Product Act (711/2022) (Applies to all EOMs)	Fertiliser Act (meststoffenwet; https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0004054/2024-01-01), Fertilizer Implementing regulation (uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet;	JANUARY 28, 2013. - Royal Decree on the marketing	No national regulations for	

<p>08/12/2015) has included biochar in the Annex 2 of the national fertilizers' legislation (Legislative Decree 75/2010 and subsequent updates) in the category of "Soil improvers".</p> <p>The Ministerial Decree 10/10/2022 (GU 303 of 29/12/2022) has included biochar in</p>		<p>https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0018989/2024-01-01), Fertilizer Decree (uitvoeringsbesluit Meststoffenwet; https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0019031/2024-01-01), The Environment and Planning Act (Omgevingswet, https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0037885/2024-01-01/0), Environmental activities decree (Besluit activiteiten leefomgeving, https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0041330/2024-01-01), Environmental quality decree (Besluit kwaliteit leefomgeving, https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0041313/2024-01-01)"</p>	<p>and use of fertilizers, soil improvers and growing substrates.</p>	<p>biochar using as EOM</p>
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	the Annex 13 of the national fertilizers' legislation (Legislative Decree 75/2010 and subsequent updates) in the category of "Fertilizers used in organic agriculture"					
Date of entry into force		11 October 2023	The Implementing Regulation is changed regularly (about monthly), and is based on the Decree, and the Decree is based on the Act.	Published in the Moniteur Belge on March 13, 2013		
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive)	Regulatory	Regulatory	Regulatory	Regulatory	Regulatory	

e, agreeme nt)					
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)	The Ministerial Decree 06/22/2015 (GU 186 of 08/12/2015) has included biochar in the Annex 2 of the national fertilizers' legislation (Legislative Decree 75/2010 and subsequent updates) in the category of "Soil improvers". The Ministerial	The purpose of the Fertiliser Products Act (711/2022) is to ensure that all fertiliser products placed on the market in Finland are safe, of good quality and suitable for plant production. The Act also aims to promote the use of by-products suitable for use as fertilisers, provided that they have a proven positive effect on plant growth and do not cause damage or danger to humans, animals, plants or the environment. Finland's soils and inland waters are more acidic than in other EU countries. Because of these exceptional soil and water conditions, special efforts are needed to control and reduce soil-related and other environmental risks in Finland. One of the main priorities in this context is to ensure the high quality and safety, including low heavy metal content, of fertiliser products used in agriculture, horticulture, landscaping and forestry. Fertiliser products include the following type groups (similarly as product function categories in the EC Regulation 2019/1009): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fertilisers • liming materials • soil improvers • growing media • biostimulants • fertilising product blend All fertilisers imported and marketed in Finland must be included in either the national list of fertiliser types or, in the case of EC fertilisers, in the list of EC fertiliser types specified in the EU Fertiliser Regulation (EC 2019/1009). The Decree of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry on Fertiliser Products (964/2023) and its Annexed lay down requirements and limit	The objective is to maintain fertile soils for agricultural production, to decrease the risk of leaching of nitrates and phosphates to groundwater and surface waters, and to prohibit deterioration of the soil quality (stand still principle or improvement regarding contaminants).	This Royal Decree, dated January 28, 2013, pertains to the marketing and use of fertilizers, soil amendments, and cultivation substrates in Belgium. Its objective is to regulate these products to ensure their quality, safety, and compliance with established	

	Decree 10/10/2022 (GU 303 of 29/12/2022) has included biochar in the Annex 13 of the national fertilizers' legislation (Legislative Decree 75/2010 and subsequent updates) in the category of "Fertilizers used in organic agriculture"	values for the product function categories and allowed component materials, similarly as in the EU Fertiliser Regulation." (Applies to all EOMs)		standards. The decree establishes rules regarding the composition, labeling, marketing, and utilization of these products, aiming to protect public health, the environment, and promote sustainable agriculture.		
For regulatory text:	RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED:	RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED:	RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED:	RAW MATERIALS ALLOWED:		
	The list of allowed raw materials, i.e. component materials, is maintained by the Finnish Food Authority (Ruokavirasto) as stated in the Decree 964/2023. The list contains information of allowed components, their origin, and characteristics. New raw materials can	The list of allowed raw materials, i.e. component materials, is maintained by the Finnish Food Authority (Ruokavirasto) as stated in the Decree 964/2023. The list contains information of allowed components, their origin, and characteristics. New raw materials can	Biochar of waste material is not included in bijlage Aa, as it is not (yet) requested by companies. Its use is therefore not allowed. Biochar made			

<p>Which raw materials are allowed for the EOM production?</p>	<p>Vegetable biomass from the agricultural, agro-industry and forestry sector</p>	<p>be included to the list through a procedure stated in the Fertiliser Products Act 711/2022. In February 2023, a draft version of the list was published: https://www.ruokavirasto.fi/kasvit/lannoitevalmisteet/laatuvaatimuks-et/ainesosaluettelo/ Biochars belong to component category 9 (Pyrolysis chars). Raw materials for biochars can, according to the list, consist of either</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • solid biofuels such as wood, plant, fruit and water biomasses (fuel class A and B products in standard SFS-EN ISO 17225-1:2021); or • sewage sludge consisting of sludge from municipal wastewater treatment, settling or septic tank sludge, sludge from other property-based or combined wastewater treatment system at farms, dry toilet waste or other wastewater treatment sludge." <p><i>This is different depending on EOM</i></p>	<p>from materials that are not regarded as waste can be used as other organic fertiliser if the requirements for composition are met.</p>	<p>Ligneous plants</p>		
<p>Which production process is allowed?</p>	<p>PRODUCTION PROCESS ALLOWED: Pyrolysis and gasification</p>	<p>PRODUCTION PROCESS ALLOWED: In component category 9 biochars need to be treated through thermochemical conversion technology, where the amount of oxygen is limited. The process conditions must reach 180 °C for at least two seconds when treating plant-based biomasses. If sewage sludges are used as raw material, the temperature must reach 500 °C for 5 minutes. <i>This is different depending on EOM</i></p>		<p>PRODUCTION PROCESS ALLOWED: Pyrolysis of woody plants</p>		
<p>Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical)</p>	<p>CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCED EOM: Parameter:</p>	<p>CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCED EOM: With biochars, the molar ratio of H and organic-C in the end-product needs to be under 0.7. The test needs to be executed to water- and ash-free fraction of the material, where organic-C content remains under 50%. The PAH16 content is limited to 6 mg per kg of dry matter. <i>This is different depending on EOM</i></p>		<p>CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCED EOM: [mg/kg of</p>	<p>Parameter Corg (% d.m.)</p>	

<p>and biological al) that the produce d EOM has to fulfill?</p>	<p>1) Corg (% d.m.) ≥ 20 > 60 Class 1; 30-60 Class 2 2) Ashes 550°C (% d.m.) ≤ 60 < 10 Class 1; 10-40 Class 2 3) pH 04-4) Electrical conductivity (mS/m) ≤ 1000 ≤ 100 in substrates 5) Humidity (% m/m) ≥ 20 for dusty products 6) H:Corg ≤ 0.7</p>	<p>"Organic fertilisers • Organic fertilisers need to contain organic carbon and nutrients, which have biological origin. The following limits are not to be exceeded: - As 40 mg/kgDM - Hg 1 mg/kgDM - Cd 1.5 mg/kgDM - Cr 300 mg/kgDM - Cu 600 mg/kgDM - Pb 100 mg/kgDM - Ni 70 mg/kgDM - Zn 1500 mg/kgDM - (Cu and Zn can be exceeded if there is detected deficiency in the agricultural soil) - Pathogen limits: - Salmonella spp: Absence in 25 g or 25 ml - Escherichia coli or Enterococcaceae 1 000 cfu in 1 g or 1 ml - Organic fertiliser has to contain at least of one primary nutrient 1% by mass. The total concentration of primary nutrients needs to be at least 2% by mass. In a solid organic fertiliser, organic carbon content needs to be at least 10% by mass. "Organic soil improvers • A solid organic soil improver shall contain at least 15% of dry matter and the organic carbon content shall be at least 7.5% by mass. • A liquid organic soil improver shall contain at least 2% organic carbon by mass, or the primary nutrient content needs to be in total 0.2% by mass. • The following limits are not to be exceeded: - As 40 mg/kgDM - Hg 1 mg/kgDM - Cd 1.5 mg/kgDM</p>		<p>dry matter] Substantial qualities whose content must be guaranteed Cadmium 1,5 Chrome 90 Cuivre 10 0 Mercure 1 Nickel 30 Plomb 12 0 Zinc 40 0 PCB (sum 7) 0,2 or 0,8</p>		
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<p>Growth test suitable with spring barley and chinese cabbage 7) Pb (mg/kg d.m.) ≤ 140</p> <p>limits for all amendments 8) Cd (mg/kg d.m.) ≤ 1.5</p> <p>limits for all amendments 9) Cu (mg/kg d.m.) ≤ 230</p> <p>limits for all</p>	<p>- Cr 300 mg/kgDM - Cu 600 mg/kgDM - Pb 100 mg/kgDM - Ni 70 mg/kgDM - Zn 1500 mg/kgDM - (Cu and Zn can be exceeded if there is detected deficiency) - Pathogen limits: - Salmonella spp: Absence in 25 g or 25 ml - Escherichia coli or Enterococcaceae 1 000 cfu in 1 g or 1 ml"</p> <p>Applies to all EOMs</p>		<p>HAP (sum 16) 4 or 6 Dioxine (PCDD/F) 20 ng eq tox ODM/DM Chlore 3 % DM C org mi n 50% DM H/C org (carbonatation level) maximum 0,7</p>		
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<p>amendments 10) Zn (mg/kg d.m.) ≤ 500</p>					
<p>limits for all amendments 11) Ni (mg/kg d.m.) ≤ 100</p>					
<p>limits for all amendments 12) Hg (mg/kg d.m.) ≤ 1.5</p>					
<p>limits for all amendments 13) Cr VI (mg/kg d.m.) ≤ 0.5 limits for all</p>					

	<p>amendments 14) PAHs (mg/kg d.m.) ≤ 6</p> <p>Σ PAH16 15) PCBs (mg/kg d.m.) ≤ 0.5</p> <p>16) PCDD/PCDF (ng/kg d.m.) WHO toxicity eq. ± 9</p>					
<p>For incentives: Is there any incentive dedicated to the agricultural application of</p>	<p>No</p>	<p>No, only investment support available Applies to all EOMs</p>		<p>No</p>	<p>No</p>	

the EOM?						
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2.2.2 Which is the national regulatory framework of your country about the use of EOMs in agricultural fields, if different from the European regulations reported in the previous section 2.1?

Country	Italy	Finland	Nederland	Belgium	Waloon	Lithuanian
Name of the policy		Government Decree on Limiting Certain Emissions from Agriculture (1250/2014) and Government Decree on Use of Phosphorus Containing Fertiliser Products and Manure (205/2022)				

		<i>Applies to all EOMs</i>				
Date of entry into force						
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive, agreement)		Regulatory				
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)		The Government Decree on Limiting Certain Emissions from Agriculture (1250/2014), known as 'Nitrates Decree', aims to reduce nitrogen emissions caused by the storage and use of manure and other organic fertiliser products and the use of inorganic fertiliser products. In the Decree, the whole of Finland is defined as a				

		<p>nitrate vulnerable zone and thus it controls nitrogen fertilisation in all farms across the country. This Decree implements the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC), and it applies to both manure and all fertiliser products (except liming products) specified in the Fertiliser Product Act (539/2006). It also applies to processed or non-processed by-products in farms that are utilised as fertilisers.</p> <p>Legislation on phosphorus fertilisation was renewed in January 2023 when the 'Phosphorus</p>				
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		<p>Decree', i.e. the Government Decree on Use of Phosphorus Containing Fertiliser Products and Manure (64/2023) was laid down under Fertiliser Act (711/2022). It is the first stricter regulation for phosphorus fertilisation in Finland. The aim is to reduce phosphorus loads to water bodies and to reduce the highest phosphorus concentrations in fields, while at the same time safeguarding the phosphorus needs of crops. The Decree regulates the use of phosphorus</p>				
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		fertilisation in agriculture, horticulture, green areas, and landscaping.				
<p>For regulatory text:</p> <p>Are there limits to the maximum applicable amounts of the EOM in specific areas (Natura 2000, Nitrate Vulnerable Zones, etc.)?</p>		<p>LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT</p> <p>In the ‘Nitrates Decree’ (1250/2014) the limit for total N is 170 kg/ha/year for the whole Finland, when using farm animal manure and organic fertiliser products. The Decree also regulates on the annual maximum amount of soluble N (kg/ha) for various crops in mineral and organic soil. If soluble N exceeds 150 kg/ha, N amount needs to be split into at</p>	<p>LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT</p> <p>The application norms on the basis of N and P. Fertilizer Implementing regulation (uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet). Application norm for P depends on P soil status, and if arable or grassland. Application norm for N depends on crop, use of catchcrop, and is decreased if soil has a certain status as: groundwaterprotection area, nutrient pollutants area (paragraph 28 of Uitvoeringsregeling meststoffenwet).</p>			

		<p>least two applications at least two weeks in between. After September 1, the amount of soluble N in manure and organic fertiliser products spread may not exceed 35 kg/ha.</p> <p>In the 'Phosphorus Decree' (64/2023), the fertilisation limits are calculated based on total phosphorus content in manure and fertiliser products with the exceptions; 60% of the total phosphorus in sewage sludge is taken into account (and in for animal manure, until</p>				
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		<p>31.12.2027), and 40% of total phosphorus in ash and biochar is taken into account. Phosphorus fertilisation must be applied with crop-specific need and yield, and taking the soil phosphorus status into account. Maximum level for phosphorus fertilisation is given by crop and soil phosphorus status in the Annex 1 of the Decree. Soil phosphorus status categories are given by soil type and soil organic matter content in the Annex 2 of the Decree. The phosphorus rates of the manure</p>				
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		<p>exemption in Annex 1 may be used when only livestock manure is used for phosphorus fertilisation. The Decree also promotes phosphorus recycling (and manure processing) by allowing a maximum of 5 kilograms of phosphorus per hectare to be given, a) if otherwise the fertilisation would be prohibited by high soil phosphorus status, and b) phosphorus is derived from the phosphorus separation of manure or digestate; and (3)</p>				
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		the ratio of total nitrogen to total phosphorus in the fraction generated by the phosphorus separation of manure or digestate is not less than 10."				
Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) of the EOM so that it can be used as soil amendment?		These decrees do not set limits for EOM characteristics. Limits are defined in the Decree of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry on Fertiliser Products 964/2023 (see 2.2.1)				
Are there some techniques of application or scheduled timelines to be respected?		CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EOM TO BE USED AS SOIL AMENDMENT: APPLICATION TECHNIQUES OR SCHEDULED TIMELINES				

	<p>"Decree 1250/2014 defines timelines and application techniques for nitrogen fertilization in manures and other fertiliser products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The spreading of manure and organic fertilisers on fields is prohibited from the beginning of November until the end of March. • Fertilisers may not be applied to snow-covered or frozen soil or to soil saturated with water. • Manure and organic fertiliser products applied to the surface of the field shall be incorporated into 				
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		<p>the soil within 24 hours of application, except when applied to the crop with a trailing hose or by broadcast application.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For field parcels covered with a crop over winter, from 15 September onwards manure and organic fertiliser products may only be spread by injection, except in the case of manure spreading prior to a crop to be sown in autumn." 				
<p>For incentives: Is there any incentive dedicated to the</p>		<p>"The direct support through CAP (common agricultural policy) in the form of the agri-</p>				

<p>agricultural application of the EOM?</p>		<p>environmental support schemes, which are related to EOMs. Example of this is the “Field parcel-specific measure to promote the circular economy” as defined in Decree 78/2023 (Government Decree on the agri-environmental support scheme). In this measure, the farmer needs to apply either slurry, urine, liquid fraction separated from slurry or liquid organic fertiliser using injection or mulching equipment or add organic material with a dry matter content of at least</p>				
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		<p>20%. Organic material can be</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • organic fertilizers; • organic soil improvers; • mixtures of organic fertilisers and organic soil improvers; • dry manure or composted manure obtained from another farm; • dry fraction separated from slurry." 				
Other comments		<p>The Decrees on phosphorus and nitrogen fertilisation are valid for all farmers in Finland. CAP measures are available only to those applying support.</p>				

FINLAND

Biochar

2.2.3 Are there other policy instruments, in your country, which can have an indirect impact on the use of EOMs in agricultural soils?

Name of the policy instruments	Type (regulatory, incentive, agreement)	General scope	Impact on EOMS use in agricultural fields
Decree of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry on Fertiliser Products 964/2023 (in Finnish: Maa- ja metsätalousministeriön asetus lannoitevalmisteista 964/2023)	Regulatory	Old version of the decree, under which fertiliser products can be produced until the end of year 2024	
The nutrient recycling scheme (Government Decree on for biogas plants to promote the production of recycled fertiliser products in the years	Incentive	The nutrient recycling scheme is a new aid scheme that aims to create a market for recycled fertilisers, thereby promoting their use and increasing the utilisation of agricultural and water management biomass as a raw	Supports the processing of digestates (especially digestate-based phosphorus). Likely increases the amount of processed digestate-based fertiliser products in the Finnish market. The aid is applicable only for biogas plants and is available between years 2024 and 2026.

		material for fertiliser products.	
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Manure

2.2.1 Which is the national regulatory framework of your country about the production of EOMs, if different from the European regulations reported in the previous section 2.1?

Country	Italy	Finland	Nederland	Lithuania	Belgium	Walloon
Name of the policy	Ministerial Decree 25 February 2016, n. 5046 which has "General technical criteria and standards for the regional regulation of the agronomic use of livestock effluents and waste water, as well as	Decree of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry on Fertiliser Products 964/2023 (in Finnish: Maa- ja metsätalousministeriön asetus lannoitevalmisteista 964/2023). The decree regulates the applicable raw materials, production processes and characteristics of the products. The regulation is in force under the Fertiliser Product Act (711/2022)	Fertiliser Act (meststoffenwet; https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0004054/2024-01-01), Fertilizer Implementing regulation (uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet; https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0018989/2024-01-01), Fertilizer Decree (uitvoeringsbesluit Meststoffenwet; https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0019031/2024-01-01), The Environment and Planning Act (Omgevingswet, https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0037885/2024-01-01/0), Environmental activities decree (Besluit activiteiten leefomgeving, https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0041330/2024-01-01), Environmental quality decree (Besluit kwaliteit leefomgeving, https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0041313/2024-01-01)"	1. Ministry of Environment of the Republic of Lithuania and Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania order 14 July 2005, No. D1-367/3D-342 "Description of environmental requirements for		

	for the production and agronomic use of digestate			manure and slurry management"		
				2. Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania order 29 May 2019 , No. 3D-332 "On the approval of the description of requirements for the use of the fertilizer products"		

Date of entry into force	25 February 2016	11 October 2023	The Implementing Regulation is changed regularly (about monthly), and is based on the Decree, and the Decree is based on the Act. All have been updated on January 1st, 2024.	1. 30 July 2005 published in "Valstybės žinios" the official publication of legal acts of the Republic of Lithuania, No. 92-3434. Valid from 31 July 2005, newest version of the order 14 March 2024. 2. 29 May 2019 published in register of legal acts on		
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				website, No. 8499. Newest alteration 3 April 2023, No. 3D-203 published in register of legal act on website, No. 6173		
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive, agreement)	Regulatory	Regulatory	Regulatory	Regulatory		
Short description of the policy (general objective, scope)	Ministerial Decree n. 5046 of 25 February 2016 represents	The purpose of the Fertiliser Products Act (711/2022) is to ensure that all fertiliser products placed on the market in Finland are safe, of good quality and suitable for plant production. The Act also aims to promote the use of by-products suitable for use as fertilisers, provided that they have a proven positive effect on plant growth and do not cause damage or danger to humans, animals, plants or the environment. Finland's soils and inland waters are more acidic than in other EU countries. Because of these exceptional soil and water conditions, special efforts are	The objective is to maintain fertile soils for agricultural production, to decrease the risk of leaching of nitrates and phosphates to groundwater and surface waters, and to prohibit deterioration of the soil quality (stand still principle or	1.The purpose of the No.D1-367/3D-342 "Description of		

<p>of action, ecc...)</p>	<p>ts the referenc e legislatio n for the adoption of the Action Program mes defined pursuant to the Nitrates Directive . The decree n. 5046 repealin g the Ministerial Decree of 7 April 2006. The Decree lays down the</p>	<p>needed to control and reduce soil-related and other environmental risks in Finland. One of the main priorities in this context is to ensure the high quality and safety, including low heavy metal content, of fertiliser products used in agriculture, horticulture, landscaping and forestry. Fertiliser products include the following type groups (similarly as product function categories in the EC Regulation 2019/1009):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fertilisers • liming materials • soil improvers • growing media • biostimulants • fertilising product blend <p>All fertilisers imported and marketed in Finland must be included in either the national list of fertiliser types or, in the case of EC fertilisers, in the list of EC fertiliser types specified in the EU Fertiliser Regulation (EC 2019/1009). The Decree of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry on Fertiliser Products (964/2023) and its Annexed lay down requirements and limit values for the product function categories and allowed component materials, similarly as in the EU Fertiliser Regulation."</p>	<p>improvement regarding contaminants).</p>	<p>environm ental requirem ents for manure and slurry managem ent" is to establish requirem ents for manure and slurry managem ent in order to prevent surface and underground water pollution and reduce air pollution. The provision s of the descriptio n are</p>		
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<p>criteria and general technical rules for the agricultural use of manure, sewage and digestate in order to enable the nutrients and soil improvers contained therein to play a useful role on agricultural soil, achieving a conciliatory, soil</p>			<p>mandatory for persons who keep farm animals and/or keep (store), transport and/or use manure and/or slurry for fertilizing fields, persons who receive manure and/or slurry, and institutions controlling this activity.</p> <p>2. The purpose</p>	
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<p>improver , irrigation , fertigation n or correctiv e effect on the land subject to agricultu ral use, in accordan ce with the quantita tive and temporal require ments of the crops. The rule is integrate d with the</p>			<p>of No. 3D-332 "The description of the requirements for the use of fertilizing products" is to determine the requirements for the use of fertilizing products applied to entities of agricultural activity, in order to reduce the negative impact on the life and health of animals and</p>	
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	applicati on of the provision s of Part Three of Legislativ e Decree No. 152/200 6.			people, as well as the environm ent.		
For regulato ry text: Which raw material s are allowed for the EOM producti on?	The digestate used for agronom ic use must derive (pursuan t to article 22 of Ministeri al Decree no. 5046 "Product ion of digestate ") from anaerobi c	The list of allowed raw materials, i.e. component materials, is maintained by the Finnish Food Authority (Ruokavirasto) as stated in the Decree 964/2023. The list contains information of allowed components, their origin, and characteristics. New raw materials can be included to the list through a procedure stated in the Fertiliser Products Act 711/2022. In February 2023, a draft version of the list was published: https://www.ruokavirasto.fi/kasvit/lannoitevalmisteet/laatuvaatimukset/aineosaluettelo/ Both slurry and manure originating from livestock production are applicable EOMs under the Animal By-Product regulation (EC 142/2011) and the national regulation (Act on Animal By-products 517/2015)."	Manure is allowed as input for EOM production. These EOM products remain considered as manure in legislation. Various non-feed products end up in manure: products that are used in the stable as bedding materials for cows and other animals, such as straw, flax, sawdust, lime, rock flour, clay materials, sand.	Manure - pure or processed animal and/or poultry feces or a mixture of litter and animal feces;		

<p>digestion systems fed by materials, whether used alone or mixed together, such as straw, mowing and pruning as well as other non-dangerous agricultural material pursuant to article 185, paragraph 1, letter f) of Legislative</p>				
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<p>the Decree n. 152/2006; agricultural material deriving from dedicated agricultural crops; from livestock effluents; from sewage; from the vegetation waters of the oil mills and humid pomace in accordance with Law n. 574/199</p>				
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<p>6; residues agri-food activity; from animal by- products used in compliance with the provisions of EC Regulation n. 1069/2009 and from agricultural and forestry material not intended for human consumption identified in</p>				
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<p>table 1B of the Ministerial Decree of 6 July 2012. The agro- industrial digestate is produced by the anaerobic digestion plant fed by sewage, residues from agri-food activities , vegetation water from oil mills and wet</p>				
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<p>pomace, and animal by-products. Such materials must originate from agricultural or agri-food activities carried out by the same undertaking that has the management or ownership of the plant or come from agricultural or agri-food enterpris</p>				
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<p>es associate d or associate d with the interfar m plant; originate from an agricultu ral or agri-food producti on process of which they form an integral part, and be used to feed the anaerobi c digestion plant. Finally, these substanc</p>				
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<p>es must not be dangerous or polluted.</p> <p>Digestate and agro-industrial digestate cannot be produced by anaerobic digestion plants fed by grass cuttings or other plant material used for the safety or remediation</p>				
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	<p>operations of contaminated sites and by grass cuttings or other material coming from land intended for the production of food crops.</p>				
<p>Which production process is allowed?</p>		<p>The Animal By Product Act (517/2015) and the Decree of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry on animal byproducts (783/2015) facilitate the implementation of EU animal by-product regulations regarding the use and disposal of animal by-products and animal-derived products, including manure and slurry. Some national privileges are given in the Act and Decree. If manure and slurry are used, for example, on the same farm where they originate or given to neighbouring farm, no treatment is needed. If manure is marketed as a fertiliser product, processing is needed. Processing can be e.g. composting (process reaching 55 C for 14 days), or anaerobic digestion in meso- or thermophilic conditions. In addition, manure can be thermally treated and processed into dry powder or pellets (end-product's moisture content under 10%) or incinerated into ash.</p>			

<p>Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) that the produced EOM has to fulfill?</p>	<p>PRODUCTION P CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCED EOM: PROCESS ALLOWED: The regulated characteristics of manure and slurry depend, whether the manure is alienated between farms, or marketed as a fertiliser product. If divided between farms, the manure should not contain risk for serious infectious disease. If manure is marketed within Finland, it needs to fulfil pathogen limits (no Salmonella, E.coli under 1000 cfu/g). If manure products are marketed outside Finland, the EU Animal By-Product Regulations is applied. "Organic fertilisers • Organic fertilisers need to contain organic carbon and nutrients, which have biological origin. The following limits are not to be exceeded: - As 40 mg/kgDM - Hg 1 mg/kgDM - Cd 1.5 mg/kgDM - Cr 300 mg/kgDM - Cu 600 mg/kgDM - Pb 100 mg/kgDM - Ni 70 mg/kgDM - Zn 1500 mg/kgDM - (Cu and Zn can be exceeded if there is detected deficiency in the agricultural soil) • Pathogen limits: - Salmonella spp: Absence in 25 g or 25 ml - Escherichia coli or Enterococcaceae 1 000 cfu in 1 g or 1 ml • Organic fertiliser has to contain at least of one primary nutrient 1% by mass. The total concentration of primary nutrients needs to be at least 2% by mass. In a solid organic fertiliser, organic carbon content needs to be at least 10% by mass. "</p>			
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		<p>"Organic soil improvers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A solid organic soil improver shall contain at least 15% of dry matter and the organic carbon content shall be at least 7.5% by mass. • A liquid organic soil improver shall contain at least 2% organic carbon by mass, or the primary nutrient content needs to be in total 0.2% by mass. • The following limits are not to be exceeded: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As 40 mg/kgDM - Hg 1 mg/kgDM - Cd 1.5 mg/kgDM - Cr 300 mg/kgDM - Cu 600 mg/kgDM - Pb 100 mg/kgDM - Ni 70 mg/kgDM - Zn 1500 mg/kgDM (Cu and Zn can be exceeded if there is detected deficiency) • Pathogen limits: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Salmonella spp: Absence in 25 g or 25 ml - Escherichia coli or Enterococcaceae 1 000 cfu in 1 g or 1 ml" 				
For incentives: Is there any incentive dedicated to the production of energy associated	Yes The DL 228/21 (Budget Law 2019) provided for the extension of incentives for Biogas	No, only investment support available		No		

<p>ed with the EOM co-production?</p>	<p>Plants from 2021 to 2022. In detail, it encourages the creation by entrepreneurs of electricity production plants powered by biogas with a maximum power of 300 kw. The incentive is granted if the plants are fed at least</p>				
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<p>80% by livestock manure and material s mainly derived from the same farms and the remainin g 20% from second harvest crops. In 2023 the first public calls for the construc tion of new biometh ane plants or for the conversi on of the</p>				
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<p>biogas plant pursuant to DM 15/09/2022 that defines the new incentives for biomethane were launched. Companies to access the calls must submit the title of authorization to the construction and operation of the plant</p>				
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<p>valid and effective, the estimate of connection to the network accepted (in case of connection to the network with obligation to connect to third parties), the certificate of conformity of sustainability of biofuels and bioliquids as</p>				
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<p>defined by DM 14/11/2019 and the certificate of greenhouse gas savings specific to the intended use of biomethane. In addition, the companies must have the digestate storage tanks covered with biogas recovery for a volume</p>				
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<p>of 30 days. During the construction of the biogas plant, the producer must have documentation to demonstrate the traceability of biomass and its traceability. The National Recovery and Resilience Plan</p>				
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<p>(PNRR) for the agriculture sector, it envisages an investment of EUR 1.92 billion for the measure on the development of biomethane and the promotion and dissemination of ecological practices in the biogas production phase in order</p>				
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<p>to reduce the use of synthetic fertilisers, increase the supply of organic matter in the soils and create poly consortia for the centralized treatment of digestate and effluents with production of fertilizers of</p>				
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<p>organic origin. The measure aims to promote innovation and diversification of agricultural enterprises and contributes to combating climate change and improving air quality by reducing the volatilisation of ammonia</p>				
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<p>Other comments</p>	<p>Possibility of selling it as fertilizer pursuant to Legislative Decree n. 75/2010. The dried digestate has been included among the nitrogenous fluid organic fertilizers pursuant to Legislative Decree n. 75/2010 (updated with the</p>				
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legislative decree of 1 March 2022 of the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies - published in the Official Journal n. 108 of 10 May 2022).						
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2.2.2 Which is the national regulatory framework of your country about the use of EOMs in agricultural fields, if different from the European regulations reported in the previous section 2.1?

Country	Italy	Finland	Nederland	Lituania	Belgium	Waloon
Name of the policy	Ministerial Decree 25 February 2016, n. 5046 which has "General technical criteria and	Government Decree Government Decree on Limiting Certain	Fertilizer Implementing regulation (uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet),	1. Ministry of Environment of the Republic of Lithuania and Ministry of		Sustainable Nitrogen Management Program (PGDA, version IV: Walloon Government Order of February 23, 2023, published on April 05, 2023)

	standards for the regional regulation of the agronomic use of livestock effluents and waste water, as well as for the production and agronomic use of digestate	Emissions from Agriculture (1250/2014) and Government Decree on Use of Phosphorus Containing Fertiliser Products and Manure (205/2022)	and the Environmental activities decree (Besluit activiteiten leefomgeving)	Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania order 14 July 2005, No. D1-367/3D-342 "Description of environmental requirements for manure and slurry management" 2. Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania order 29 May 2019, No. 3D-332 "On the approval of the description of requirements for the use of the fertilizer products"		
Date of entry into force	25 February 2016					
Type of policy instrument (regulatory, incentive, agreement)	Regulatory	Regulatory	Regulatory	Regulatory		Regulatory

<p>Short description of the policy (general objective, scope of action, ecc...)</p>	<p>Ministerial Decree n. 5046 of 25 February 2016 represents the reference legislation for the adoption of the Action Programmes defined pursuant to the Nitrates Directive. The decree n. 5046 repealing the Ministerial Decree of 7 April 2006. The Decree lays down the criteria and general technical rules for the agricultural use of manure, sewage and digestate in order to enable the nutrients and soil improvers contained therein to play a useful role on agricultural soil, achieving a conciliatory, soil improver,</p>	<p>The Government Decree on Limiting Certain Emissions from Agriculture (1250/2014), known as 'Nitrates Decree', aims to reduce nitrogen emissions caused by the storage and use of manure and other organic fertiliser products and the use of inorganic fertiliser products. In the Decree, the whole of Finland is defined as a nitrate vulnerable zone and thus it controls nitrogen fertilisation in all farms across the country. This Decree implements the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC), and it applies to both</p>	<p>The Implementing regulation gives limits to the amount of applied N and P (§ 3 Uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet). The Environmental activities decree, and Environmental quality decree lays down more practical rules, such as when you are allowed to use certain fertilisers.</p>	<p>1.The purpose of the No. D1-367/3D-342 "Description of environmental requirements for manure and slurry management" is to establish requirements for manure and slurry management in order to prevent surface and underground water pollution and reduce air pollution. The provisions of the description are mandatory for persons who keep farm animals and/or keep (store), transport and/or use manure and/or slurry for</p>		<p>The Walloon law PGDA (Programme de Gestion Durable de l'Azote) aims to regulate and mitigate the impacts of nitrogen use on the environment, particularly water pollution and air quality issues. It includes provisions such as limits on nitrogen fertilizer application, requirements for livestock effluent management, incentives for adopting more sustainable farming practices to reduce nitrogen leaching and other forms of pollution. The primary goal is to promote more responsible nitrogen use in agriculture to safeguard ecosystem health and human populations.</p>
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	<p>irrigation, fertigation or corrective effect on the land subject to agricultural use, in accordance with the quantitative and temporal requirements of the crops.</p> <p>The rule is integrated with the application of the provisions of Part Three of Legislative Decree No. 152/2006.</p>	<p>manure and all fertiliser products (except liming products) specified in the Fertiliser Product Act (539/2006). It also applies to processed or non-processed by-products in farms that are utilised as fertilisers.</p> <p>Legislation on phosphorus fertilisation was renewed in January 2023 when the 'Phosphorus Decree', i.e. the Government Decree on Use of Phosphorus Containing Fertiliser Products and Manure (64/2023) was laid down under Fertiliser Act (711/2022). It is</p>		<p>fertilizing fields, persons who receive manure and/or slurry, and institutions controlling this activity.</p> <p>2. The purpose of No. 3D-332 "The description of the requirements for the use of fertilizing products" is to determine the requirements for the use of fertilizing products applied to entities of agricultural activity, in order to reduce the negative impact on the life and health of animals and people, as well</p>		
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		the first stricter regulation for phosphorus fertilisation in Finland. The aim is to reduce phosphorus loads to water bodies and to reduce the highest phosphorus concentrations in fields, while at the same time safeguarding the phosphorus needs of crops. The Decree regulates the use of phosphorus fertilisation in agriculture, horticulture, green areas, and landscaping."		as the environment.		
For regulatory text: Are there limits to the maximum	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT For the use of digestate it is	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT "In the 'Nitrates Decree' (1250/2014) the	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT The application norms on the basis of N and P.	LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT 1. No.D1-367/3D-342		LIMITS TO THE MAX APPLICABLE AMOUNT Art.R.207. Without prejudice to compliance with article R.214, § 1, organic nitrogen inputs may not exceed an average of 115 kg per hectare of arable land and an average of 230 kg per hectare of grassland, including returns to the soil by grazing animals, over one year

<p>applicable amounts of the EOM in specific areas (Natura 2000, Nitrate Vulnerable Zones, etc.)?</p>	<p>necessary to focus attention on articles 22 to 34 of Ministerial Decree n. 5046. The digestate used for agronomic purposes pursuant to this decree is excluded from the application of the waste regulations as it is considered a by-product. Limitations are foreseen for the contribution of digestate and effluents to the soil based on the designation of the area. The agronomic use of effluents must comply with the annual nitrogen limit of 170 kg per hectare in areas vulnerable to nitrates and 340 kg per hectare per</p>	<p>limit for total N is 170 kg/ha/year for the whole Finland, when using farm animal manure and organic fertiliser products. The Decree also regulates on the annual maximum amount of soluble N (kg/ha) for various crops in mineral and organic soil. If soluble N exceeds 150 kg/ha, N amount needs to be split into at least two applications at least two weeks in between. After September 1, the amount of soluble N in manure and organic fertiliser products spread may not exceed 35 kg/ha.</p>	<p>Fertilizer Implementing regulation (uitvoeringsregeling Meststoffenwet). Application norm for P depends on P soil status, and if arable or grassland. Application norm for N depends on crop, use of catch crop, and is decreased if soil has a certain status as: ground water protection area, nutrient pollutants area (paragraph 28 of Uitvoeringsregeling meststoffenwet).</p>	<p>"Description of environmental requirements for manure and slurry management": During a calendar year, the amount of nitrogen entering the soil (by fertilizing with manure) cannot exceed 170 kg/ha. 2. The purpose of No. 3D-332 "The description of the requirements for the use of fertilizing products" During a calendar year, the total amount of nitrogen (N), including from manure and slurry, entering</p>		<p>and for the entire declared agricultural area of the farm, depending on whether it is arable land or grassland. Art. R.208. § 1. On a given parcel of land, and without prejudice to compliance with article R.207, organic fertilizers are applied in proportions such that, over the two to seven successive years during which the plot is farmed either as arable land or grassland, depending on the rotation used, the average amount of organic nitrogen applied in any one year does not exceed: 1° 115 kg per hectare of arable land; 2° 230 kg per hectare of grassland. § 2 The maximum organic nitrogen input per plot, over one year, is set at 230 kg Norg. per hectare." Art. R.214. § 1. In vulnerable zones, over one year and for the whole of the farm's utilized agricultural area, organic nitrogen inputs to the farm's relevant areas may not exceed an average of 170 kg per hectare of utilized agricultural area.</p>
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	<p>year in non-vulnerable areas. The agronomic use of digestate (article 26 of Ministerial Decree no. 5046) and agrozootechnical digestate (article 28 and 29 of Ministerial Decree n. 5046) must respect the nitrogen limit in the field of 170 kg per hectare per year in areas vulnerable to nitrates and 340 kg per hectare per year in non-vulnerable ones. The percentage of digestate coming from the digestion of non-zootechnical materials must be counted in the nitrogen balance to</p>	<p>In the 'Phosphorus Decree' (64/2023), the fertilisation limits are calculated based on total phosphorus content in manure and fertiliser products with the exceptions; 60% of the total phosphorus in sewage sludge is taken into account (and in fur animal manure, until 31.12.2027), and 40% of total phosphorus in ash and biochar is taken into account. Phosphorus fertilisation must be applied with crop-specific need and yield, and taking the soil</p>		<p>the soil cannot exceed 210 kg, phosphorus (P2O5) 90 kg and potassium (K2O) 240 kg per hectare. The amount of nitrogen (N), including from manure and slurry, can be exceeded up to 250 kg, phosphorus (P2O5) up to 150 kg and potassium (K2O) up to 300 kg per hectare when a fertilization plan is drawn up, taking into account soil tests (not older than 3 year) results and the potential yield possible for that type of soil and granulometric</p>		
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	<p>be reported in the agronomic use. The agronomic use of manure and digestate shall be prohibited:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - for 90 days, with the exception of bovine manure, sheep and goats and equidae, for which the regions may also provide for application in the winter months, except in the period between 15 December and 15 January when used on pastures, permanent or alternating grassland and in the pre- pre- field planting of horticultural crops; - 90 days in the case of manure-assimilated materials, with the 	<p>phosphorus status into account. Maximum level for phosphorus fertilisation is given by crop and soil phosphorus status in the Annex 1 of the Decree. Soil phosphorus status categories are given by soil type and soil organic matter content in the Annex 2 of the Decree. The phosphorus rates of the manure exemption in Annex 1 may be used when only livestock manure is used for phosphorus fertilisation. The Decree also promotes phosphorus recycling (and manure</p>		<p>composition, it is suggested to use higher amounts of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium.</p>		
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	<p>exception of poultry meat dehydrated by a rapid process with a dry matter content exceeding 65% for which the prohibition is 120 days; - for manure and similar substances 90 days in soils with grassland, cereal-autumn-winter, vegetable crops, tree crops with permanent grassing or with crop residues and in preparation for early spring sowing; and 120 days in land destined for other types of cultivation; - for a continuous period of at least 60 days from 1 December to 31</p>	<p>processing) by allowing a maximum of 5 kilograms of phosphorus per hectare to be given, a) if otherwise the fertilisation would be prohibited by high soil phosphorus status, and b) phosphorus is derived from the phosphorus separation of manure or digestate; and (3) the ratio of total nitrogen to total phosphorus in the fraction generated by the phosphorus separation of manure or digestate is not less than 10."</p>				
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	January of each year. The application of manure shall be prohibited within 25 metres of water bodies located in wetlands defined by the Ramsar Convention.					
Which are the characteristics (physical, chemical and biological) of the EOM so that it can be used as soil amendment?		CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EOM TO BE USED AS SOIL AMENDMENT: These decrees do not set limits for EOM characteristics. Limits are defined in the Decree of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry on Fertiliser Products 964/2023 (see 2.2.1)	CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EOM TO BE USED AS SOIL AMENDMENT: There are no composition requirements for manure regarding contaminants; but it has to be safe for use The composition of manure is regulated somewhat via feed. EU norms for Cu and Zn, and national laws on P content have influence on			CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EOM TO BE USED AS SOIL AMENDMENT: No

			manure composition			
Are there some techniques of application or scheduled timelines to be respected?		<p>APPLICATION TECHNIQUES OR SCHEDULED TIMELINES:</p> <p>“Decree 1250/2014 defines timelines and application techniques for nitrogen fertilization in manures and other fertiliser products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The spreading of manure and organic fertilisers on fields is prohibited from the beginning of November until the end of March. • Fertilisers may not be applied to snow-covered or frozen soil or to soil saturated with water. 	.	<p>APPLICATION TECHNIQUES OR SCHEDULED TIMELINES</p> <p>1. No.D1-367/3D-342</p> <p>"Description of environmental requirements for manure and slurry management":</p> <p>It is prohibited to fertilize and/or spread manure and/or slurry from November 15th until March 20th. It is forbidden to add manure and/or slurry to frozen, soaked, flooded, snow-covered land or to spread it on such land. From November 15</p>		<p>APPLICATION TECHNIQUES OR SCHEDULED TIMELINES</p> <p>"See spreading calendar, page 3</p> <p>https://www.protecteau.be/sites/default/files/2024-02/PE_FeuilletPGDAIV_%28275x390%292402_01_0.pdf</p> <p>"</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manure and organic fertiliser products applied to the surface of the field shall be incorporated into the soil within 24 hours of application, except when applied to the crop with a trailing hose or by broadcast application. • For field parcels covered with a crop over winter, from 15th September onwards manure and organic fertiliser products may only be spread by injection, except in the case of manure spreading prior to a crop to be sown in autumn.” 		<p>until November 30 it is possible to fertilize only perennial meadows, pastures, arable land with plant cover (seeded, planted with plants) with a slope of no more than 5%, the amount of nitrogen entering the soil cannot exceed 40 kg per hectare, it is forbidden to spread liquid manure and/or slurry closer to as 5 m to the shoreline of the water body. From March 1st until March 20th it is possible to fertilize only perennial</p>		
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				<p>meadows, pastures, arable land with plant cover (seeded, planted with plants) with a slope of no more than 5%, it is forbidden to spread liquid manure and/or slurry closer than 5 m to the shoreline of the water body. Fertilization with manure and/or slurry is prohibited from June 15 until August 1, except fallows, meadows, pastures and areas where winter crops will be grown. It is forbidden to fertilize corn crops from July 10 until August</p>	
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				<p>1. It is prohibited to fertilize with liquid manure and/or slurry on Saturdays, Sundays, and public holidays closer than 100 m from a residential building without the resident's written consent, which can also be provided by electronic means of communication (e-mail or text message), which allow to ensure text integrity, irrevocability and identification of the consenting person; closer than 300 m from the boundary of the</p>	
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				urbanized territory without the written consent of the ward elder, which can be provided by electronic means of communication (e-mail or text message), which allow to ensure the integrity of the text, immutability and identification of the person giving the consent. It is prohibited to spread liquid manure and/or slurry closer than 3 m to the upper edges of the drainage ditches.		
For incentives:	Digestate can be applied directly to	The direct support through CAP	Yes			No

<p>Is there any incentive dedicated to the agricultural application of the EOM?</p>	<p>the soil without further treatment than normal practices such as dehydration, sedimentation, centrifugation and drying, filtration, solid-liquid separation, stripping, nitrification, denitrification and phytopurification. The application of manure on agricultural soil requires treatment operations. Yes The DL 228/21 (Budget Law 2019) provided for the extension of incentives for Biogas Plants from 2021 to 2022. In detail, it encourages the creation by</p>	<p>(common agricultural policy) in the form of the agri-environmental support schemes, which are related to EOMs. Example of this is the “Field parcel-specific measure to promote the circular economy” as defined in Decree 78/2023 (Government Decree on the agri-environmental support scheme). In this measure, the farmer needs to apply either slurry, urine, liquid fraction separated from slurry or liquid organic fertiliser using injection or mulching equipment or add</p>	<p>The P application norm depends on soil P status AND is higher for certain types of organic-rich fertilizer. This enables farmers that have fields with low soil organic matter levels, to use more straw-rich manures, solid-fraction of manure, champost.</p>			
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Commentato [G(1): Compost?

	<p>entrepreneurs of electricity production plants powered by biogas with a maximum power of 300 kw. The incentive is granted if the plants are fed at least 80% by livestock manure and materials mainly derived from the same farms and the remaining 20% from second harvest crops. In 2023 the first public calls for the construction of new biomethane plants or for the conversion of the biogas plant pursuant to DM 15/09/2022 that defines the new incentives for biomethane were launched.</p>	<p>organic material with a dry matter content of at least 20%. Organic material can be</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • organic fertilizers; • organic soil improvers; • mixtures of organic fertilisers and organic soil improvers; • dry manure or composted manure obtained from another farm; • dry fraction separated from slurry." 				
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	<p>Companies to access the calls must submit the title of authorization to the construction and operation of the plant valid and effective, the estimate of connection to the network accepted (in case of connection to the network with obligation to connect to third parties), the certificate of conformity of sustainability of biofuels and bioliquids as defined by DM 14/11/2019 and the certificate of greenhouse gas savings specific to the intended use of biomethane. In addition, the</p>					
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	<p>companies must have the digestate storage tanks covered with biogas recovery for a volume of 30 days.</p> <p>During the construction of the biomethane plant, the producer must have documentation to demonstrate the traceability of biomass and its traceability.</p> <p>The National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) for the agriculture sector, it envisages an investment of EUR 1.92 billion for the measure on the development of biomethane and the promotion and dissemination of ecological practices</p>					
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	in the biogas production phase in order to reduce the use of synthetic fertilisers, increase the supply of organic matter in the soils and create poly consortiums for the centralized treatment of digestate and effluents with production of fertilizers of organic origin. The measure aims to promote innovation and diversification of agricultural enterprises and contributes to combating climate change and improving air quality by reducing the volatilisation of ammonia					
Other comments	Possibility of selling it as fertilizer	The Decrees on phosphorus and				

	<p>pursuant to Legislative Decree n. 75/2010. The dried digestate has been included among the nitrogenous fluid organic fertilizers pursuant to Legislative Decree n. 75/2010 (updated with the legislative decree of 1 March 2022 of the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies - published in the Official Journal n. 108 of 10 May 2022).</p>	<p>nitrogen fertilisation are valid for all farmers in Finland. CAP measures are available only to those applying support.</p>				
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FINLAND

Manure

2.2.3 Are there other policy instruments, in your country, which can have an indirect impact on the use of EOMS in agricultural soils?

Name of the policy instruments	Type (regulatory, incentive, agreement)	General scope	Impact on EOMS use in agricultural fields
Decree of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry on Fertiliser Products 964/2023 (in Finnish: Maa- ja metsätalousministeriön asetus lannoitevalmisteista 964/2023)	Regulatory	Old version of the decree, under which fertiliser products can be produced until the end of year 2024	
The nutrient recycling scheme (Government Decree on for biogas plants to promote the production of recycled fertiliser products in the years	Incentive	The nutrient recycling scheme is a new aid scheme that aims to create a market for recycled fertilisers, thereby promoting their use and increasing the utilisation of	Supports the processing of digestates (especially digestate-based phosphorus). Likely increases the amount of processed digestate-based fertiliser products in the Finnish market. The aid is applicable only for biogas plants and is available between years 2024 and 2026.

		agricultural and water management biomass as a raw material for fertiliser products.	
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NEDERLAND

Manure

2.2.3 Are there other policy instruments, in your country, which can have an indirect impact on the use of EOMs in agricultural soils?

Name of the policy instruments	Type (regulatory, incentive, agreement)
7th Action Programme of the Netherlands	Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/2069 of 30 September 2022 on granting a derogation requested by the Netherlands pursuant to Council Directive 91/676/EEC concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources (notified under document C(2022) 6859) (Only the Dutch version is authentic)
Fertiliser Act	Artikel 18a Meststoffenwet

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